

MORU BIOETHICS AND ENGAGEMENT ANNUAL REPORT 2024

MORU has an active community and stakeholder engagement programme coordinated by a dedicated engagement team led by Professor Phaik Yeong Cheah. We study ethical issues in particular those involving in research in low-resource settings and with vulnerable populations. We run internal engagement training and support researchers at MORU and collaborative sites in ethics/engagement components of large biomedical studies.

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PhD students (primarily based in other departments but supervised or co-supervised by Phaik Yeong Cheah):

- Naomi Waithira (Bangkok, DPhil Student, University of Oxford)
- Carlo Perrone (Chiangrai, PhD Student, Open University)
- Sandhya Dhawan (Bangkok, DPhil Student, Open University), study title: Laboratory Safety Assessments of Facility and Environment (LABSAFE), co-supervised by Bhensri Naemiratch.

B) International committees

- Phaik Yeong Cheah is a member of the WHO COVID-19 Task Force on Good Participatory Practices in Emerging Pathogens
- Phaik Yeong Cheah is the Co-Chair of the Data Sharing Working Group of the COVID-19 Clinical Research Coalition and member of the Ethics Working Group of the COVID-19 Clinical Research Coalition
- Phaik Yeong Cheah is a member of the Steering Committee of the Global Forum for Bioethics Research

C) Bioethics & Engagement Publications

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2. Ean, M., Tripura, R., Sothea, P., Savoeun, U., Peto, T. J., Bunthynn, S., ... Adhikari, B. (2024). A youth advisory group on health and health research in rural Cambodia. *Global Bioethics*, 35(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/11287462.2024.2361968>
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6. Perrone C, Kanthawang, N, Cheah PY, Intralawan D, Lee SJ, Nedsuwan S, Fuwongsitt B, Wangrangsimakul T, Greer RC, Community engagement around scrub typhus in northern Thailand: a pilot project, *Transactions of The Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, Volume 118, Issue 10, October 2024, Pages 666–673, <https://doi.org/10.1093/trstmh/trae028>
7. Perrone, C., Kanthawang, N. & Cheah, P.Y. A hill tribe community advisory board in Northern Thailand: lessons learned one year on. *Int J Equity Health* 23, 241 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-024-02323-z>
8. Pokharel S, Adhikari B, Johnson T, Cheah PY. Interventions to address antimicrobial resistance: an ethical analysis of key tensions and how they apply in low- income and middle-income countries. *BMJ Glob Health.* 2024 Apr 3;9(4):e012874. doi: 10.1136/bmjgh-2023-012874.
9. Poomchaichote, T., Kiatying-Angsulee, N., Boonthaworn, K. et al. Embedding community and public voices in co-created solutions to mitigate antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in Thailand using the ‘Responsive Dialogues’ public engagement framework. *Antimicrob Resist Infect Control* 13, 71 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13756-024-01416-2>
10. Shaw J, Ali J, Atuire CA, Cheah PY, Español AG, Gichoya JW, Hunt A, Jjingo D, Littler K, Paolotti D, Vayena E. Research ethics and artificial intelligence for global health: perspectives from the global forum on bioethics in research. *BMC Med Ethics.* 2024 Apr 18;25(1):46. doi: 10.1186/s12910-024-01044-w.
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12. Waithira N, Mukaka M, Kestelyn E, Chotthanawathit K, Thi Phuong DN, Thanh HN, Osterrieder A, Lang T, Cheah PY. Data sharing and reuse in clinical research: Are we there yet? A cross-sectional study on progress, challenges and opportunities in LMICs. *PLOS Glob Public Health.* 2024 Nov 20;4(11):e0003392. doi: 10.1371/journal.pgph.0003392.

D) Grants obtained in 2024

- Wellcome Trust. ‘Strengthening Community Engagement Infrastructure in Thailand and Cambodia £136,074. 1 Jan 2024 – 31 Dec 2026 (Principal Investigator PY Cheah, Co-Is Anne Osterrieder, Napat Khirikoekkong, Supa-at Asarath, Nipaphan Kanthawang, Carlo Perrone)

E) Engagement Activities

1) *Public Advisory Groups*

At the core of MORU’s engagement programme is a network of adult and youth advisory groups that provide us with valuable insights and advice on how to conduct our research and health programmes in the most ethical and impactful way.

Tak Province Community Ethics Advisory Board (T-CAB)

Currently T-CAB has 17 members, ages between 30s to 60s, 9 women and 8 men. Since 2009, T-CAB have reviewed and discussed more than 130 health and research topics, members remained interested in increasing health accessibility for border population which is a major challenge facing this population.

In January 2024, T-CAB celebrated its 15th Anniversary held at Mr. Somchai Netnirandon’s house in Hwy Nam Nak village. The event attended by T-CAB members, staff member of SMRU, BHF and MORU.

The findings of the T-CAB evaluation have been drafted and are being submitted for publication.

No	Date	Summary Agenda
1	13/01/2024	<p>Study finding:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Explore the perspectives of Tak Province Community Advisory Board (T-CAB) members on the benefits, challenges and impact of the group toward research and healthcare on Thai-Myanmar border” by Ms. Napat Khirikoekkong <p>Dialogue Drama on TB/HIV Awareness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “The Contrite Heart” by CEPE Team
2	03/02/2024	<p>Studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Migration and Marginality of health towards migrants: Exploring immunization barriers towards migrant children at the age of 5 and under in Phop Phra and Mae Ramat District along Thai-Burma border” by Naw Hai Ti Ti - “Safety & efficacy of FD-TACT (Fixed dose Triple ACT) for Plasmodium Falciparum malaria” by Dr. May Thu Thu Aung - “Optimal Packaging of Primaquine Assessment Project (OPPAP)” by Jindaporn Wirachonphaophon <p>Lecture:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Filariasis” by Dr. Aung Pyae Phy
3	04/05/2024	<p>Study:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Seroprevalence of antibodies against Diphtheria, Pertussis, and Tetanus, measles and polio pathogen among Children under Seven Years Old in two Districts of Karen Division, Myanmar” by Dr. Thaw Htwe Min

		Training:
		- "Parent Engagement and Family Dialogue" by Thara Nay Thar (Suwannimit Foundation)
4	22/06/2024	Studies:
		- "Gestational Weight Gain and maternal and neonatal outcomes, by BMI and height, in a migrant population along the Thai-Myanmar border: a retrospective cohort study" by Widi Yotyingaphiram and Dr. Mary Gouws
		- "To evaluate the usability and acceptability of a new lateral flow test for TB among healthcare workers" by Widi Yotyingaphiram and Dr. Aung Pyae Phyto
5	10/08/2024	Study:
		- "Field Evaluation of back-scattering Dr. Stephane Proux dark field microscopy for ultrafast & ultrasensitive Malaria diagnosis" by Dr. Stephane Proux
		Study Progress:
		- "Seroprevalence of antibodies against Diphtheria, Pertussis, and Tetanus, measles and polio pathogen among Children under Seven Years Old in two Districts of Karen Division, Myanmar" Saw Win Tun and Saw Baw Nyaw
6	21/09/2024	Study:
		- "Mass Drug Administration of Tafenoquine for P. vivax Radical Cure: Pilot Safety and feasibility study" by Dr. Min Thu Thu Aung and Jindaporn Wirachonphaopong
		Study finding:
		- "Migration and Marginality of health towards migrants: Exploring immunization barriers towards migrant children at the age of 5 and under in Phop Phra and Mae Ramat District, along Thai-Burma border" by Naw Hai Ti Ti
7	28/10/2024	Group Discussion:
		- SEACOV study and activity with T-CAB by MORU
8	26/10/2024	Study findings:
		- COVID-19 pandemic, pregnancy care, perinatal outcomes in Easter Myanmar and North-Wester Thailand: a retrospective marginalized population cohort" by Dr. Taco Jan Prins
		- Determinants and trends of preterm birth and small for gestational age in the migrant and refugee population on the Thai-Myanmar border: A 30-year population cohort study" by Dr. Aung Myat Min
9	30/11/2024	Study:
		- "Non-invasive sample collection for Tuberculosis biomarker development and validation" by Dr. May Thu Thu Aung
		TB information sharing/presentation:
		- "Role of communities in TB control activities, Thai Myanmar border" by Dr. Aung Than

Young Person's Advisory Group (Y-PAG), Thai-Myanmar Border

The Young Person's Advisory Group (Y-PAG) on Thai-Myanmar border was established in December 2021 and currently has 12 members, 2 male, 9 female and 1 identifying as 'other'. Members of Y-PAG are youth aged between 15 to 24 years old, and members of the Sexual Reproductive Health and Rights (SRHRs) network. The border Y-PAG is named Youth Aileen's Potency, which means power and value of young lights; the members came up with this name by themselves.

Y-PAG members requested a capacity building on mental health topics, after they observed the struggles young people face. Many endured difficulties for having been forced to leave their family in Myanmar to seek educational opportunity in Thailand, struggling with sexual identity, and other daily challenges as a

migrant youth without legal documents. The aim of this workshop was to expand their understanding on mental health, coping mechanisms, support their peers, and reduce stigma surrounding mental health, particularly in border communities where knowledge and understanding remain limited.

In 2024, the Y-PAG had 3 discussions with researchers and project leaders on the following topics:

No.	Date	Summary Agenda
1	30/03/2024	<p>Presentation of project/research/activity</p> <p>Sensitive information and data</p> <p>Definitions of data from THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL</p> <p>Review the definitions and terminologies</p> <p>Discussion: what information/data is sensitive and why is it sensitive</p>
2	23-24/06/2024 *a two-day workshop	<p>Capacity Building: Mental Health Awareness and Building Resilience Workshop</p> <p>Delivered and facilitated by: Dr. Grace (Tin Mar San), Psychologist, EMDR Therapist, Trauma Counsellor and Trainer</p> <p>Workshop agenda details</p> <p>Day 1</p> <p>Awareness and Recue Stigma</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mental health and Stigma <p>Stress related topics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nature of Stress <p>Types of Stressors and Stress Reactions</p> <p>Stress related topics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Group discussion - Self-assessment <p>Coping and Managing Stress</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Healthy ways of coping and unhealthy ways of coping - How to manage stress <p>Day 2</p> <p>Trauma</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Types of traumas - Cases of traumas - Signs and Symptoms of Trauma <p>Building Resilience</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is resilience and how do you understand resilience? - The important factors of the resilience
3	21/09/2024	<p>Discussion: Health and research topics on Thai-Myanmar border area</p> <p>Day 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the major health burdens facing young people living along Thai-Myanmar border area? - Have you heard of any research being done on those health topics? Please tell us more about it - How do these health burdens impact the lives, physical and other aspects of young people? - What do you think should be done? - What health topic you would like researcher to research on or to pay more attention on? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Please say more why such topics need more attention/need research? o Who would benefit from research and how? <p>Who should researcher speak/discuss with if they are going to design a research to address health needs?</p>

4	21/12/2024	Review of MRCT translated posters from English to Burmese for finalisation. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Poster 1: What is Assent – Poster 2: Assent to consent – Poster 3: What is Clinical Research – Poster 4: What happens at the end of a research study
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Since June 2024, Plan International and Help Without Frontiers (HWF) are no longer founding members of Y-PAG, after the funding period of Sexual Reproductive Health and Rights has ended. Currently founding members are MORU, SMRU, MAP foundation and SNF foundation, remaining members are from MAP and SNF youth network.

The Bangkok Health Research Ethics Interest Group (HREIG)

Group background

The Bangkok HREIG, established in August 2019, is one of the five Community Advisory Board organized by MORU. The group's remit is to provide advice and feedback on MORU research projects, in particular those that do not have a defined local or disease community (e.g., data re-use) and to provide their opinion, feedback, and experience to MORU researchers to ensure that MORU; project and researches are ethically sounded. Meetings are facilitated by the HREIG team staff consisting mainly of Supanat Ruangajorn, Dr. Kanpong Boonthaworn and Tassawan Poomchaichote, with occasional assistance from the Bioethics and Engagement staff: Natinee Kulpijit, Dr. Bhensri Naemiratch, Supa-at Asarath, who help facilitate and translate during breakout session activities..

Group update and progress from 2023 - 2024

Since 2023, the membership term with the 'first generation' members has been concluded. The HREIG's first batch ran from August 2019 with the activity concluding in 2023. Despite term end, the member remain in contact with MORU to become alumni, where they will be notified of any MORU activities and engagement opportunities that might be of interests.

HREIG 2.0

In early 2024, the team worked on public advertising to recruit the second group of members, or 'HREIG 2.0'. With over 200 applications submitted, 20 were chosen as members. These are people from different walks of life, age, and occupation who reside in Bangkok metropolitan areas. HREIG 2.0's first session was organized in June of 2024 and the group meets regularly on a monthly basis.

Sessions and activity

From June 2024 to February 2025, there have been a total of *9 meeting sessions*. Session details are summarized in the listed below:

<u>Date</u>	<u>Session and activities</u>	<u>Session details</u>
2024		
<u>June 22nd</u>	HREIG orientation and SEACOVARIANT By Supanat Ruangajorn, Tassawan Poomchaichot	Introduction to MORU and SEACOVARIANT pilot session to familiarize members with HREIG activities and to obtain feedback for the SEACOVARIANT team.

<u>July 13th</u>	AMR cartoon peer review By Tassawan Poomchaichote, Dr. Kanpong Boonthaworn	Feedback and review the AMR cartoon contest target contestant population and theme to prepare for the contest organized in 2024.
<u>August 17th</u>	Capacity building: Ethics in research and Clinical trial By Dr. Bhensri Naemiratch, Tassawan Poomchaichote	To provide members with background to significance of ethics in research and clinical trials.
<u>September 21st</u>	ARSYNAL-FC study: Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV) By Dr. Simon Boyd	Feedbacks, opinions and suggestions on ARSYNAL-FC project communication and participant recruitment strategy.
<u>October 19th</u>	Sensitive data in the context of Thai society By the HREIG team	Explore sensitivity and importance of each data type in perspective of Thai people, compared with sensitive data contained in PDPA and GDPR
<u>November 16th</u>	AMR engagement consultation By Dr. Direk Limmathurotsakul	The session aims to brainstorm and feedback for public experience and view on AMR problems to seek for potential research topics for future research.
<u>December 14th</u>	Feedback on MORU Aims By Prof. Phaik Yeong Cheah	Annual summary of the group activity throughout the year and activity for suggestion on MORU aims to better explain and translate them to Thai according to the context they perceived.
2025		
<u>Jan 18th</u>	MOTIP AMR Hackathon 2025 By Grid Ganjina	Encourage participants to ideate projects coping with AMR situation in Thailand
<u>Feb 8th</u>	Introduction to informed consent By Prayoon Yuentrakul	Capacity building session for the members to understand and associate the importance of informed consent process and implications concerning informed consent in studies through group activities.

In 2024, the ‘HREIG-EVAL’ evaluation study completed data analysis and defining the thematic framework used for the study. The manuscript is in preparation.

Chiang Rai Community Advisory Board (CR-CAB)

This project is led by Nipaphan Kanthawang and Carlo Perrone and facilitated by Bulakorn Tinoi. It was started through funding from the Wellcome Trust “BEPE Public Engagement Bursaries Scheme” 2020-2025. While investigating the experiences of researchers and participants, comprehension, research literacy, and underestimation of burdens were found. Such issues are amplified in members of hill-tribe ethnic groups, who represent approximately 20% of the population of Chiangrai province.

In order to carry out research that is the CAB was established in September 2023, allowing us to maximize research benefits and minimize its burdens as well as make sure the projects are relevant to local needs and conducted ethically. Following preliminary work with local stakeholders, 15 members from 7 ethnic groups, aged between 42 and 68 were included.

Current status

The first CAB meeting was in November 2023, with meetings taking place monthly (with few exceptions). Meetings last 2.5-3 hours and take place in the city of Chiang Rai at the Hill Tribe Museum and Education Center. Meetings start with a summary of the meeting from the previous months, followed by one or more presentations on past, current, or planned studies, and related questions to and from CAB members, with the double aim of sharing findings and ideas and obtaining practical feedback from CAB members on presented studies e.g. how to carry out projects in a context and culturally appropriate fashion etc. Additionally during the meetings topics of interest are discussed. Finally, updated health and interested situations locally by CAB members.

The CR-CAB activities are being evaluated through self-administered questionnaires completed by members at each meeting (information from November 2023 until December 2024), key findings rated the topics presented as “very important (highest level of three points scale) for their community 78% of time and quite important (middle level of a three point scale) 20% of the time. They had learned “a lot” 88%, and 89% stated that they planned to share their new knowledge with others. Attendance averages 74%.

In 2024, we published “A hill tribe community advisory board in Northern Thailand: lessons learned one year on” (DOI: [10.1186/s12939-024-02323-z](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-024-02323-z)).

Since first meeting in November 2023 – December 2024, the CR-CAB had 14 meetings with researchers and project leaders on the following topics:

No.	Date	Summary Agenda
1	17/11/2023	Presentation of research findings of the study - Causes of acute undifferentiated fever and the utility of biomarkers in Chiangrai
2	19/12/2023	Presentation of research findings of the study - Prevalence and associated factors with scrub typhus infection among hill-tribe people in Mae Fah Luang, Chiangrai, Thailand.
3	19/1/2024	Review of planned study documentation - School and community-based intervention for early detection of post-COVID mental health and long-term effects in Thai border schools: combined geospatial approach for network of support and policy Implications
4	16/2/2024	Presentation of research findings, advice sought on how to feed individual viral hepatitis results back to participants - Overview of disease burden in rural South and Southeast Asia : A cross-sectional household health survey with questionnaire interviews and selected laboratory tests
5	15/3/2024	Engagement project; Discussion and seek opinion for future pandemics - Conversation preparedness for future pandemics with CR-CAB
6	19/4/2024	Presentation of research findings, suggestions on how to improve comprehension of participant information - The challenges and potential solutions of achieving meaningful consent amongst research participants in northern Thailand: a qualitative study.
7	17/5/2024	Planned research study, advice sought on how to perform informed consent - Quick and easy scrub typhus diagnostic tools

8	14/6/2024	Presentation of research findings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Effects of a smartphone application for children and Family self-management on eating and physical activity behaviors among overweight late school-aged children.
9	19/7/2024	Presented studies, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidelines for a poster on clinical research: obtaining consent and assent in children (obtained suggestion from CR-CAB members) - Vulnerability and agency in research participants' daily lives and the research encounter: A qualitative case study of participants taking part in scrub typhus research in northern Thailand. (Present research findings) - Covid vaccine safety. (CR-CAB interested topic)
10	31/7/2024	Review the planned research document <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-creating information materials with communities to improve the Informed Consent process. (Special meeting to obtain CR-CAB feedback on study document, material)
11	16/8/2024	Present planned research study <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - -Co-creating information materials with communities to improve the Informed Consent process.
12	4/10/2024	Review the planned research document <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A community health podcast on understanding, preventing and managing scrub typhus
13	22/11/2024	Review research tools (study questionnaires) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -School and community-based intervention for early detection of post-COVID mental health and long-term effects in Thai border schools: combined geospatial approach for network of support and policy Implications
14	13/12/2024	Off-site meeting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community Engagement and site visit activity

Youth Advisory Group on Health and Research Engagement (YAGHRE), Siem Pang, Cambodia
Activities in 2024

In January 2024, the Siem Pang Youth Advisory Group on Health and Research Engagement (YAGHRE) group consisted of ten grade 11 students (16-22 years old, half are female). The group's activities are detailed below:

Date	Activities
22nd Jan 2024	4 th batch of youth students was recruited in January 2024, a group consisted of ten grade 11 students (16-22 years old, half are female).
23rd Jan 2024	Introduction of MORU to YAGHRE members batch 4. In this meeting, YAGHRE members were briefed about what MORU is, what are its objectives, where does it work and why is it important to work as YAGHRE member
Jan 2024 to Jun 2023	Skill transfers on using computer. YAGHRE members batch 4 were taught by batch 4 on how to use computers, and then on specific programs such as MS words, MS Excel, MS Power Points, apps and browsers to support their work for engagement activities with the supported and observation from MORU staff
June 2024	First article on youth advisory group on health and research is online: https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/11287462.2024.2361968
Jul-2024 to Sep-2024	Skill transfers on using camera and Drone. YAGHRE members batch 4 were taught by batch 3 on how to use camera and drone to prepare the photos and video-footage.
15th to 18th October 2024	Health research workshop: PY visited Siem Pang and met with YAGHRE members from all the batches. The workshop was held to identify common health problems in the community through group discussions and interviews with villagers.
21st October 2024	Youth group members attended the first meeting on <i>antimicrobial resistance and ethics: public and community engagement through circus arts in Cambodia</i> at Angkor hospital for children, Siem Reap. The participants are CNM-COMRU-MORU-AHEAD-Phare Circus.
Jan-2024 to Dec-2024	Youth group have attended training on Diabetes, Reproductive health on AIDS/STIs and Antimicrobial resistance (AMR). They were trained by MORU researchers and Siem Pang health centre chief. These training sessions were participatory primarily through dialogue and discussions.
9th January 2024 to 27th Dec 2024	Health education about Dengue fever, Diabetes, Reproductive health on AIDS/STIs and AMR at 6 schools (5 secondary schools and one high school in Siem Pang). YAGHRE members went and disseminated the learnt knowledge to fellow students using the tools they prepared such as leaflet and poster. A total of 2897 school students have been engaged by the YAGHRE members, as well as 16112 community members from Jan- Dec 2024. (see Appendix)
Jan-2024 to Dec-2024	Video production, YAGHRE members batch 3 and batch 4 have produced three videos in 2024 such as: Dengue fever, Diabetes and a video capturing the visit by Wellcome Trust guests in Siem Pang. These three videos have been uploaded in YouTube channel [https://www.youtube.com/@YouthAdvisoryGrouponHealth] and Facebook page of Youth group [https://web.facebook.com/YouthAdvisoryGrouponHealth] .
Jan-2024 to Dec-2024	Create health information materials: YAGHRE members have created leaflet and poster on 4 topics with key messages on Dengue fever, Diabetes and Reproductive health on AIDS/STIs and AMR. YAGHRE members distributed leaflets and posters to students in schools so they can take them home and spread the word to their family members.
Dec-2024	A total of 10 YAGHRE members have graduated in 2024, and 20 are currently participating in our engagement program.

In 2024, the group's activities reached a total of 2897 school students, and a total of 16,112 community members. The topics of the activities were: dengue fever, diabetes, reproductive health on AIDS/STIs and AMR.

Date	YAGHRE activities	Number of school students	Number of Community members
9-Jan-24	Dengue fever health education at Serey Tuoth Secondary school	370	1941
4-Mar-24	Diabetes health education at Sre Sambo secondary school	132	700
5-Mar-24	Diabetes health education at Sekong secondary school	82	483
12-Mar-24	Diabetes health education at Techo Siem Pang high school	324	1926
29-Mar-24	Diabetes health education at Serey Tuoth secondary school	288	1700
9-May-24	Diabetes health education at Santepheap secondary school	114	787
25-May-24	Diabetes health education at Prek Meas secondary school	153	873
21-Jun-24	Reproductive health on AIDS/STIs health education at Sre Sambo secondary school	117	657
5-Jul-24	Reproductive health on AIDS/STIs health education at Sekong secondary school	87	185
19-Jul-24	Reproductive health on AIDS/STIs health education at Santepheap secondary school	104	713
9-Aug-24	Reproductive health on AIDS/STIs health education at Techo Siem Pang high school	286	1710
13-Aug-24	Reproductive health on AIDS/STIs health education at Prek Meas secondary school	165	944
29-Aug-24	Reproductive health on AIDS/STIs health education at Serey Tuoth secondary school	328	1571
13-Dec-24	AMR health education at Sre Sambo secondary school	160	880
27-Dec-24	AMR health education at Prek Meas secondary school	187	1042
	Total	2897	16112

Films and videos co-produced by YAGRHE members and researchers

- Activities during the Wellcome Trust visited Siem Pang [<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nIcriPSQcUs&t=101s>]
- Dengue Fever [<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fuQKnIT8TSU&t=13s>]
- Diabetes [<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=27upckJQuXA>]

A poster co-created by researchers and YAGHRE members was presented at the Oxford Tropical Network-2024, Bangkok, Thailand.

Engaging a youth advisory group on health and health research in Siem Pang, Cambodia

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Introduction

- There is a lack of access to health education and health services
- Young students can play a significant role by providing health education in the community particularly in the remote areas.
- Young people are energetic, eager to learn and to get involved in activities that empower them.
- They can support research participants, particularly children and provide feedback to researchers

Objectives

- To create a sustainable network of young students
- To build capacity of the students on soft skills on presentation, communication, and leadership skills
- To provide knowledge on common diseases and public health problems to the students
- To provide knowledge on basics of health research and ethics.
- To embed young people's voices in research.
- To co-create health and research related information and communications materials.
- To improve community health through health education
- To identify and better understand on the issues and concerns of research participants

Materials and methods

- 1st batch of youths was recruited in May 2021 (the group now is an alumni)
- 2nd batch was recruited in May 2022, 1/by 3rd batch in May 2023
- Students were from grade 11 and were chosen based on students' interest and teachers' recommendations as a best fit for YAGHRE.
- Each activity was documented through fieldnotes, photographs and videos.
- Afterwards, interactive discussions were conducted with the youth group and members of the collaboration, including public health engagement experts.
- All data underwent content analysis using the theory of change approach to synthesize prominent outcomes.

Progress and achievement

The posters below were created by youth members!

Key messages on Malaria

Goals and outcomes

1. Increased respect towards individuals, communities, and stakeholders
2. Increased trust and relationships
3. Improved health and research literacy
4. Improved uptake of health and research interventions
5. Improved community health

Way forward

1. Evaluation of YAGHRE activities
2. Exploration of opinions and perspectives of community and participants on ongoing or recently completed clinical research studies.
3. Exploration of potential ways to improve engagement activities, consent process and research procedures

For more activities from YAGHRE members, please scan following QR codes

For more information, please contact us Bpin@tropmedres.ac

Workshop July 2024

1. Interview villagers

Key Details:

- Location: Khes Svay Village, Prek Meas Commune, Siem Pang District
- Date of interviews: October 17, 2024
- Purpose: To explore the issues, health concerns, and habits related to drug or health service usage in the community.

Insights from Interviews:

- **Demographics:** Respondents provided details like age, sex, and education level, with many villagers having limited or no formal education.
- **Family dynamics:** Families are typically large, with many children.
- **Healthcare access:**
 - Most villagers seek help from private clinics for health issues.
 - A significant lack of awareness about health programs and preventive measures.
- **Common health concerns:**
 - Diseases such as typhoid, dengue, malaria, and non-communicable diseases like hypertension and diabetes.
 - Nutritional deficiencies and gynecological problems are prevalent.
- **Hygiene and sanitation:** Poor sanitation practices and lack of hygiene are widespread, contributing to various health issues.
- **Drug usage:** Many villagers lack awareness about the proper use of medicines.
- **Suggestions by villagers:**
 - More community health awareness programs.
 - Improved access to clean water and sanitation.

2. Result of YAGHRE Siem Pang Health Research Workshop

Key Themes and Findings:

- **Community Issues:**
 - Lack of clean water and hygiene, poor sanitation, and garbage disposal.
 - Alcohol and drug use contributing to domestic violence.
 - Early marriage, school dropouts, and unemployment, especially among youth.
 - Environmental issues such as deforestation and water pollution.
- **Health concerns:**
 - Major diseases: typhoid, dengue, malaria, diabetes, hypertension, and malnutrition.
 - Mental health issues and chronic illnesses such as nephrotic syndrome and STIs.
 - Widespread diarrhea, gynecological problems, and pain-related complaints.
- **Impact on community:**
 - Health issues lead to school dropouts, reduced family income, domestic conflicts, and mental health problems.
 - Poor hygiene and lack of preventive knowledge exacerbate these issues.
- **Community desires:**
 - Training and education on disease prevention and hygiene.
 - Programs addressing malnutrition, diabetes, and infectious diseases.
 - Increased outreach and support from MORU and other organizations.
 - Enhanced community awareness campaigns on health issues and hygiene.
 - Local partnerships to promote understanding and prevention.

Overall Summary:

The documents highlight significant challenges in Siem Pang, Cambodia, including:

1. Limited healthcare access and awareness.
2. Prevalence of preventable diseases due to poor hygiene and sanitation.
3. Social issues such as unemployment, education gaps, and early marriage.
4. Environmental degradation affecting water and food security.

Recommendations:

- Prioritize health education and preventive care programs.
- Improve water sanitation systems and waste management infrastructure.
- Strengthen partnerships with NGOs, health authorities, and local leaders to create sustainable solutions.
- Promote community outreach to address health, education, and social issues comprehensively.

2) CCRU public engagement activities

Co-creating information materials with communities to improve the Informed Consent process (CIMIC)

This project, led by Nipaphan Kanthawang and funded by a GHBN bursary, using community participation method, aims at finding ways to improve the informed consent process by co-creating research information materials (e.g. graphic, audio) together with communities especially hill tribes, the elderly and/or illiterate and women of childbearing age 16 or above.

The project consisted of two phases. Phase I took place in 2023 and focused on the co-creation of informative materials for potential research participants. Following workshops and focus group discussions (FGDs) with community members and after assessing which part of the informed consent process were least understood, a video explaining a particular ongoing research project was created, with versions in Thai and three hill-tribe languages (Akha, Lahu, and Mien). To develop the video, we used accessible tools (smartphones and low-cost applications), so that research or healthcare intervention projects with limited funding could use similar strategies in the future. As most of the co-creators and study participants were members of hill-tribe communities, interpreters and translators were used as needed.

Subsequently, in Phase II, from 11 to 15 November 2024, we compared the effectiveness of the informed consent process using the co-created video we produced in Phase I which was dubbed in three hill tribe languages (Akha, Lahu, and Mien). The participants in this phase were split into two groups: Group 1 received the simulated informed consent using the traditional process (verbal explanation) and Group 2 received the simulated informed consent using the traditional process (verbal explanation) plus the co-created video we made in Phase I. To compare the effectiveness of each method, a multiple-choice questionnaire with 20 closed-ended and 8 open-ended questions was given to participants after a simulated informed consent for each approach. In this phase, 21 key community figures, including hill tribe interpreters provided support to participants who required assistance with completing a questionnaire, speaking, reading, and writing in Thai language. The OxTREC has approved the study as minimal risk study and Chiang Rai Public Health Provincial Ethics Committee (PHOEC) exempted the study from EC review.

In Phase II, a total of 100 participants were recruited in the study, 68% were female, and all belonged to hill tribe ethnic minorities. The age means was 48 years old, 63% had not received formal education. During the simulated informed consent process, 58% of participants used an interpreter during the entire simulated informed consent process. In comparison to those who received traditional simulated

informed consent (verbal explanation) only (Group 1, mean: 8.62/20, $p = 0.020$ after adjusted sex, age group, literacy, highest education level, and interpreter needed), participants from Group 2, who received traditional simulated informed consent plus co-created video in their native language, showed significantly better understanding (mean: 9.80/20) when understanding was evaluated. While older participants (≥ 60 years old) demonstrated less understanding (mean: 8.18/20) than younger participants (< 60 years old, mean: 9.61/20, $p = 0.034$), participants with no formal education faced greater challenges in comprehension (mean: 1.27/20) than those with higher education levels (mean: 8.59/20, $p = 0.007$). Using open-ended questionnaires, key challenges understanding, as reported by participants, included languages and communication barriers, inconsistencies in translations by hill tribe interpreters and difficulties translating research terms into native languages. Illiteracy, interrupted education, and cognitive overload information in participant information sheets further hindered understanding, with many participants struggling to retain and explain back the information provided. The participants from Group 1 suggested that video, posters, or pictures would help them understand better, while Group 2 found that watching video can expand their understanding more and they will be benefit for older people or those with limited literacy.

The introduction of co-created materials, particularly videos in native languages, emerged as an effective strategy for enhancing comprehension. These materials were supported by visual aids like posters and the option for repeated viewings. Participants overwhelmingly favored visual and video-based materials over verbal-only explanations, highlighting the importance of community collaboration in developing culturally sensitive and accessible resources.

The project demonstrated the effectiveness of co-created materials in improving informed consent and enhancing participants' understanding of research-related information, while also building staff capacity for creating culturally relevant materials and addressing communication barriers. Lessons learned emphasized the need to consider participants' backgrounds, train interpreters for consistent and accurate translations, and engage communities in developing materials tailored to those with communication challenges. For future research, the inclusion of videos, posters, or brochures in native languages, supplemented by repeated viewings and family involvement, was recommended to ensure better comprehension. However, despite improvement, the understanding of many research concepts was still (on average) limited; highlighting the need to continue efforts to increase research literacy and comprehension in vulnerable populations.

These findings are being prepared for publication in an international journal, with plans to expand community collaborations, train hill tribe interpreters, and develop co-created materials to further enhance the informed consent process in future studies.

Scrub typhus public engagement work

Scrub typhus is highly endemic in northern Thailand, yet awareness and knowledge are low. We partnered with the primary care department of Chiang Rai Hospital and developed a community engagement project to improve awareness in communities at risk. This was carried out in two phases in Mueang and in Mae Suai districts of Chiangrai province between 2019 and 2022. After developing training materials (a video in Akha, Lahu, and Thai languages), we used a train-the-trainer approach focusing on community health volunteers who, in turn, shared the gathered knowledge with their communities [1]. In CHVs, baseline knowledge of scrub typhus was low (median of 7/13) but increased dramatically after the trainings (median 13/13). Also, feedback from participants allowed us to improve the training materials, increasing usability [2].

Following recommendations from participants, we developed an audio recording with the key messages on scrub typhus to be played on community loud-speakers. To explore upscaling potential and reduce the workload of CHVs, we compared the effectiveness of in-person trainings by CHVs, the audio track alone, and the video alone. The video was more effective in increasing scrub typhus knowledge (as summarized in table 1. Importantly, neither the audio track nor the video were less effective than frontal presentations, meaning that a simple and upscalable strategy not relying on CHVs resources could be equally effective in raising scrub typhus knowledge and awareness. Multivariable analysis did not substantially change the findings.

Table 1 - Scrub typhus knowledge by training method among community members

Characteristic	Training Method			Total, n (%)
	Flipchart/ Frontal, n (%)	Audio, n (%)	Video, n (%)	
Total	17	26	31	74
Knowledge score ¹				
- Baseline				<i>p=0.031</i>
Median (p25, p75)	1 (0-3)	2 (2-4)	1 (0-2)	2 (1-3)
- Post-training				<i>p=0.007</i>
Median (p25, p75)	6 (4-7)	5 (3-6)	7 (6-8)	6 (4-8)
Score increase				<i>p<0.001</i>
- Mean (SD)	3.9 (1.9)	2.3 (1.8)	5.2 (1.9)	3.9 (2.2)

¹= Out of a maximum score of 9

Following the experiences described above, we began a project focused on co-creating podcasts about scrub typhus with members of communities at risk, the project is led by Nidanuch Tasak. The target population are community members of five villages in Mae Fa Luang district, the villages were selected because of the high number of reported scrub typhus cases and where the population consists almost entirely of people of non-Thai ethnicity.

The project started with a series of stakeholder interviews with village heads, CHVs, and PCU staff, who recommended shooting a video as well as recording a podcast, and to include the key messages regarding scrub typhus in a narrative story, as this would be more capturing.

The resulting recordings and video are available in Akha, Lahu, Hmong, and Thai language. Four groups (one for each language) of about 20 participants will be sampled from the target villagers in order to assess their baseline knowledge of scrub typhus. Following the assessment, the video and audio tracks will be played and feedback on its clarity gathered from the audience.

Subsequently, the video and audio recording will be provided to village headsmen and CHVs for them to play at community gatherings and through village loudspeakers. Knowledge will be newly assessed after one month.

Finally, focus group discussions (FGDs) and in-depth interviews (IDIs) with community leaders and healthcare workers will be carried out, focusing on: 1-Disease understanding and awareness; 2-Behavioural impact; 3-Program effectiveness; 4-Relevance; and suggestions for improvement.

3) *Engagement around antimicrobial resistance (AMR)*

'AMR Dialogues'

After conducting a series of conversations, both online and in-person, from November 2020 to July 2022, the study team, coordinated by Tassawan Poomchaichote, compiled project findings and organized them into a booklet filled with original illustrations, written in lay language (Thai). The final version was launched on June 11st, 2023. Approximately 300 printed booklets have been shared with all project participants, policymakers, and members of public interested in AMR. The electronic PDF version can be found at <https://zenodo.org/records/8024656>, which has reached around 2,000 views and 1,000 downloads as of December 31st, 2024.

In 2024, MORU in collaboration with the AMR Dialogues network, including the Thailand Food and Drug Administration, Ministry of Public health, Thai Health Promotion Foundation and Drug System Monitoring and Development Center, co-hosted the 4th National Forum on Antimicrobial Resistance in Thailand from June 12 to 13, under the theme "Save Lives, Fight Resistance". The conference objectives were to officially launch the second National Action Plan on AMR (2023-2027) in Thailand, reaffirm political commitment and leadership in tackling AMR, strengthen the AMR network at regional, national and global levels and serve as a forum for knowledge exchange on the one health approach.

Young Cartoonist Against AMR Contest 2024

We continued our collaboration with the Drug System Monitoring and Development Center (DMDC), the AMR Dialogues project partner, to organize the 'Young Cartoonist Against AMR Contest 2024' for the World AMR Awareness Week (WAAW), a global campaign to raise awareness and understanding of AMR, celebrated from November 18-24 every year. The 2024 contest aimed to inspire and engage young people aged 15 to 22 years to become advocates for changes by raising AMR awareness through comic, under three themes: "AMR and Where to Find Them", "AMR in the next Thirty Years", and "Dancing with AMR". The competition took place from 15 October to 17 November 2024, attracting 337 entries from 45 provinces. Winners were awarded certificates of recognition and monetary awards in total of 30,000 Thai Baht.

The first place winners were second-year medical illustration students from Khon Kaen University with their piece on the theme "AMR and where to find them". The second place was a digital graphics student at the Lampang Vocational College, who applied under the theme "Dancing with AMR". Lastly, our third place went to a high school student, St. Francis Xavier Convent School, Bangkok, for her work on "AMR and where to find them".

The comic that won first place in the 2024 competition.

On 28 November 2024, in collaboration with the Drug System Monitoring and Development Center, Social Research Institute, Chulalongkorn University and Thai Health Promotion Foundation, we organized a half-day event for the World AMR awareness Week at CU Social Innovation Hub, Social Research Institute, Chulalongkorn University. The event began with a panel discussion on the current AMR situation in Thailand and the ways to tackle it. The panel consisted of policymaker on AMR, pharmacist, bioethicist and representative from the food and agriculture sector. Followed by an award ceremony for the winners of AMR cartoon contest, winners were invited to talk about their inspiration to join the campaign, and the thoughts and ideas process behind their art piece. The final session was an informal conversation on using art and comics for health communication, led by cartoonists and expert on digital art and infographics.

To continuously promote the activity for future events and raise public awareness, especially within the youth population, toward AMR issues, we conducted a separated short interview with all three winners to gain their experience joining the competition, their thought process while producing the artwork, and to share their motivation and to encourage potential participants to participate in future activities. The interview is planned to be developed into a short video to be used in our social platforms along with our collaborator to further advocate for AMR future campaigns for youth.

4) SEACOVARIANTS Project

The "Southeast Asia Initiative to Combat SARS-CoV-2 Variants" (SEACOVARIANTS) is an international collaborative project that started in November 2022, with the collaboration of researchers from Vietnam, Indonesia, Thailand, the United Kingdom and United States. The project originally aimed to develop and apply a multidisciplinary research platform for the rapid assessment of the biological significance of SARS-CoV-2 variants, thereby supporting local policymakers with evidence-based decision-making. Later, the project also expanded its scope to include any other pathogen outbreaks that may potentially become pandemics in the future, and to co-create communication and engagement framework for future pandemics.

We used the COVID-19 pandemic as a model for co-creating a communication and engagement framework for future pandemics. From January to November 2024, we conducted community dialogues facilitated by Tassawan Poomchaichote, Dr. Kanpong Boonthaworn, Natinee Kulpijit, and Supanat Ruangajorn, involving a total of 119 participants across Thailand. These dialogues gathered data about the communication challenges faced during the pandemic and information or actions required preparing for future pandemic. Diverse groups of people were impacted by COVID-19 pandemic, our project focused on hard-to-reach groups who experienced the greatest communication barriers.

To define the hard-to-reach group, we involved the project team brainstorming, consulting the Health Research and Ethics Interest Group (HREIG) and conducting a literature review to create an initial list for community dialogues. The initial list was then validated at the end of each dialogue's session to determine if the updates were needed.

No.	Stakeholder group	Selection criteria	Date of event	Number of participants
1	University students (Bangkok)	Youth and education impact	11 November 2023	20 M=13/F=7
2	Slum community in Bangkok (Klong Toei)	Slum, low resource and elderly	21 January 2024	20 M=5/F=15
3	Ethnic groups in Northern Thailand (Chiang Rai)	Remote area, religion, language barrier (minority)	15 March 2024	11 M=7/F=4
4	Health Research and Ethics Interest Group (HREIG)- Community Advisory Broad in Bangkok	Urban advisory group	22 June 2024	15 M=4/F=11
5	Migrant workers in industrial areas (Samut Sakorn)	Myanmar workers in urban (migrant/minority)	25 August 2024	16 M=3/F=13
6	Visual impairment (Bangkok)	Visual impairment (Disability)	28 August 2024	9 M=7/F=2
7	Muslim community in Southern Thailand (Pattani)	Religion/Believe	11 September 2024	14 M=8/F=6
8	Thai-Myanmar border community (Tak)	Migrant in Thai-Myanmar border	28 September 2024	14 M=7/F=7
Total number of participants				119 M=54/F=65

After completing the community dialogues, we defined hard-to-reach group in Thailand as those facing challenges due to any of the following factors: low resources, low education, limited internet or

technology access, physical or mental health problem, language barriers, physical inaccessibility due to location or time constraints, undocumented status or no ID cards, cultural and religious beliefs, and stigmatization. ' Data analysis and development of an initial communication and engagement framework are in progress.

5) Engagement related to Malaria Infection Studies Thailand (MIST)

In 2024, the Malaria Infection Studies Thailand (MIST) project prioritized participant recruitment for MIST1 and MIST2. Working in close collaboration with clinical investigators, the engagement team employed multiple approach methods, including advertisement through variety of communication channels and producing materials, such as informative videos explaining the studies, a dedicated MIST project website (<https://mist.in.th/>) serving as a central information hub, and printed brochures for distribution.

To facilitate direct interaction with potential participants, together with the Principal Investigators (PI), the engagement team has organized and conducted eight public information sessions. These sessions provided a platform for interested individuals to learn detailed information which has been tailored by the corresponding PI and team for ease of understanding about the MIST1 and MIST2 studies, it also act as a two-way communication channel for them to ask questions directly about the study team, and engage in discussions and for us to ask and alleviate any concerns they may have.

A total of 95 people attended these sessions. Beyond the structured information sessions, the MIST engagement team undertook outreach activities, connecting with over 315 individuals.

6) Pint of Science Thailand/Laos 2024

Background

Pint of Science was first organized in the UK in 2012 by a community of postgraduate and postdoctoral researchers, and is run by volunteers. It is an annual worldwide science festival, takes place over three days in the month of May, simultaneously across the world. The 'Pint of Science' aims to bring researchers and scientists to communicate their works, current research, scientific development, or demonstrate science experiments in the more accessible and comprehensible format to the public audiences in public places, for example, café, restaurant, co-working space, even the pub. The event also acts as a platform which allows science-enthusiast people to discuss directly with the people who are carrying out the research.

In 2017, the first Pint of Science Thailand was organized in Bangkok with supports by the Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU), with funding from Wellcome. Pint of Science Thailand held events every year and expanded to Chiang Rai in the northern region, namely Pint of Science Chiang Rai in 2019. Whilst the main event is held only in May, the smaller one-night events are held throughout the year as 'Pint of Science Shot!'.

Summary of PoS Thailand talks

DATE	VENUE	TOPIC	No. of attendees
13 th May 2024	Glowfish Sathorn, Bangkok Thailand	“URBAN CITY PLAN” Apiradee Kasemsook, Dean, Faculty of Architecture, Silpakorn University	45
		“TICK-BORNE PATHOGEN and NON-PATHOGEN”, Artharee Rungrojn, Microbiology Department, MORU	
		“NOVEL HOUSE DESIGN TO PREVENT DISEASES IN TANZANIA”, MORU	
14 th May 2024	Glowfish Sathorn, Bangkok, Thailand	“IS THERE HOPE FOR EFFECTIVELY CURING PARKINSON’S AND ALZHEIMER’S DISEASES IN OUR ERA?”, Suangsuda Supasai, Faculty of Tropical Medicine, Mahidol University	50
		“LAYING HEN: A PROMISING PLATFORM FOR THERAPEUTIC ANTIBODY PRODUCTION”, Charin Thawornkuno, Faculty of Tropical Medicine, Mahidol University	
		“PRACTICAL TIPS FOR PERSONAL PROTECTION AGAINST PM2.5 POLLUTION”, Arthit Phosri, Faculty of Public Health, Mahidol University	
5 th Nov 2024	Libary BKK, Victory	“Theropod Dinosaurs from Thailand”, Adun Samathi, Walai Rukhavej Botanical Research Institute, Mahasarakham University	89
		“The Rise of Paper Mills : A New Threat to Research Integrity”, Phrutsamon Wongnak, Clinical Trial Unit, MORU	
		“AMASS (AutoMated tool for Antimicrobial resistance Surveillance System)” Research to Reality, Preeyarach Klaytong, Chalida Rangsiwutisak, Microbiology, MORU	
		“Power to live with disasters : The studies in Thailand and Japan”, Juthatip Wiwattanapantuwong, Faculty of Psychology, Chulalongkorn University	

Pint of Science Thailand

Event title: Pint of Science Thailand

Venue: Glowfish Sathorn

Date: 13-14th May 2024

Organizer: Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU)

In 2024, Pint of Science Thailand event was held two days during 13-14th May 2024 and led by Associate Professor Wirichada Pan-ngum and the Thailand team.

Planning Procedures

To optimize organization and management, the organizing team strategically chose Glowfish Sathorn for this Pint of Science Thailand in May 2024. Glowfish Sathorn branch venue was chosen, as the location was easily accessible by BTS Sky train. The organizing team was also concerned about the heavy rain in May, so an indoor venue was chosen for this reason. Multiple pre-event visits were conducted, which helped with planning of the details of the event. This dedication to efficient management and generosity of volunteers are already part of the successful event.

To promote the event, MORU team sent invitation emails in advance at 1 month, 2 weeks, 1 week prior to the event. The poster was made and attached along the invitation email as well (Please see Table 1: Pint of Science Thailand online promotional poster). Apart from email invitation, there were Facebook posts as well at 2 months, 1 months, 3 weeks, 2 weeks, 1 week, 3 days in advance of the event date, and lastly on the event date.

<p>Monday 13th May 2024 Time: 6.00-8.30 PM</p> <p>Glowfish Workplace Sathorn</p> <p>PINT OF SCIENCE</p> <p>URBAN CITY PLAN</p> <p>Dr. Apradee Kasemsuk is the Dean, Faculty of Architecture, Sripakorn University. She believes that design is not something distant, but rather surrounds us and constantly influences everyone's behavior. By recognizing the interconnectedness of human health, animal health, and the health of the environment within the built environment, human can create built environments that promote the health and well-being of all living beings, fostering a more sustainable and resilient future.</p> <p>TICK-BORNE PATHOGEN AND NON-PATHOGEN</p> <p>Artharee Rungronj works as a Laboratory Technician in the Microbiology Department at MORU. Her responsibilities include conducting disease diagnosis on samples from both animals and humans using molecular techniques such as qPCR and PCR, as well as employing cell culture techniques. Additionally, she is pursuing her PhD at Mahidol University with a keen interest in studying ectoparasites, particularly ticks, which have the potential to transmit diseases and affect both animal and human populations.</p> <p>NOVEL HOUSE DESIGN TO PREVENT DISEASES IN TANZANIA</p> <p>Lorenz von Seidlein is a professor of global health based in Bangkok, Thailand. His work includes coordinating malaria elimination efforts in many countries in Southeast Asia and sub-Saharan Africa. Lorenz will talk about how Asian rural house designs with elevated bedrooms and permeable walls, may help to reduce malaria in rural Tanzania.</p> <p>Hosts: Assoc. Prof. Wirichada Pan-Ngum Registration is compulsory. Please RSVP at https://forms.gle/HsUcY2Bf5rJKsGwk9 or</p>	
<p>MORU</p> <p>Doors open at 6 p.m. Talk starts promptly at 6.30 p.m.</p> <p>FREE ENTRY</p> <p>pintofscienceth.com @pintofscienceth #pint24</p>	<p>MORU</p> <p>Doors open at 6 p.m. Talk starts promptly at 6.30 p.m.</p> <p>FREE ENTRY</p> <p>pintofscienceth.com @pintofscienceth #pint24</p>

Table 1 Pint of Science Thailand online promotional poster

Reflections and limitations/challenges

The venue is a co-working space and many public events are regularly held here. All facilities such as projection screens, microphones with speaker and projector are provided. In general, it has a fish tank designed with grandstand seats which impressed the audience. However, the event was held in May and those two days with heavy rain prohibited the audiences travelling to the event.

In order to promote the event, we have offered free PoS T-shirt for the first 20 participant who registered at the event. We found that this encouraged some of audiences came to only get the freebies, but not intend to attend the event.

Output and Conclusion

The Pint of Science Thailand took place during 13-14th May 2024 from 6PM – 8.30PM. There were 6 speakers presenting at the event. The hosts were Thailand Director, Wirichada Pan-ngum, Massaya Sirimatayanant, Carlo Perrone from Pint of Science Thailand team.

Prior to the start of the event, the final rehearsal for the speakers and organizing team to quickly run-through the event, to tests the slides, and made sure that all speakers would have control over their slides and made sure that all is set and done. The final rehearsal took place 30 minutes before the starting of the event.

During the event and Q&A sessions after the talks were done, the Kahoot! game was used as a tool to interact with the participants. The audience seem very enjoyable.

There were in total 45-50 participants showed up at both days. Despite of the heavy rain, the number of participants were impressive. The target audience are what we expected to have at this event.

Evaluation from Participants for both dates: 39 responses

What brings you to today's Pint of Science?

39 responses

Where did you see, hear, or learn about our event?

39 responses

How well did Pint of Science do to increase your interest in science?

39 responses

Venue: How do you like this venue?

38 responses

Speakers: in general, how well did they do at serving you science?

39 responses

Overall enjoyment or 'good time' you had this evening?

39 responses

What should we definitely do again next time?

- Venue & Location
 - Nice area
 - The venue is convenient
 - Seating arrangement (circle)
- Food & Drinks
 - Fantastic food
 - Free drinks! Mangosteen juice would be great
- Organization & Execution
 - Slick organization
 - Reception from staff was excellent
 - The way the event was organized: place, staff, speakers
 - Keep up the pep and energy!
- Topics & Curation
 - Nice variety of topics
 - All topics are related in some ways
 - The three talks on the first day went together really well, despite covering different areas of interest
 - Chose interesting topics with new findings
 - The selected topics were interesting and well-presented
 - Speakers had expertise and delivered talks well, answering questions effectively
 - The overall curation of topics was engaging—I could keep listening without getting bored
- Suggestions for Improvement
 - Increase discussion time
 - 30 minutes per person is just right

What can we do better next time?

- Visibility & Promotion
 - More visibility
 - Advertise more
 - Promote through various faculties, universities, and schools
- Food & Drinks
 - Not enough French fries
 - Pints of beer
 - Beer
 - If the venue serves food, it would be nice to be able to buy dinner (eat, drink, watch, and enjoy)
- Audio & Technical Improvements
 - Better audio system
 - Couldn't hear clearly because of the mics and speakers
- Venue & Space
 - The location is convenient for transportation but a bit too small and uncomfortable
 - The slight chaos—maybe that's the charm in this informal and casual setting
- General Feedback
 - Everything was good
 - Everything was done well

Any other suggestions?

- Promotion & Marketing

- More marketing to invite people to join
- Better promotion of the event
- Promote more to schools and universities—many people might not know about this event but would want to participate
- Audience & Participation
 - More mixed audience
 - I liked the science that was outside the box
- Speakers & Topics
 - More basic science speakers (physics, biology, chemistry, etc.)
 - Include more branches of science, not just public health—astronomy sounds interesting too
 - Would like to see more research related to daily life (currently good but can be improved)
- Logistics & Venue
 - Provide parking information
- Gifts & Incentives
 - Gifts should be fair for people who stay until the end
 - T-shirts for people who ask questions would be nice
- Food & Drinks
 - Beer
- General Feedback
 - Overall is fine
 - Nothing to add
 -

Event title: Pint of Science Shot Thailand

Venue: Library Victory Monument

Date: 5th November 2024

Organizer: Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU)

In 2024, we held another Pint of Science shot Thailand on 5th November 2024, led by Associate Professor Wirichada Pan-ngum and Thailand team.

Planning Procedures

To optimize organization and management, the organizing team strategically chose Library BKK at Victory Monument for this Pint of Science Shot Thailand in November 2024. Library BKK was chosen due to its location and we would like to reach the academics nearby Mahidol University. We also wanted explore the new format of venue, e.g. bar & restaurant style.

To promote the event, MORU team sent invitation emails in advance at 1 month, 2 weeks, 1 week prior to the event. The poster was made and attached along the invitation email as well (please see Figure 1 Pint of Science Shot online promotional poster). Apart from email invitation, there were Facebook posts as well at 2 months, 1 months, 3 weeks, 2 weeks, 1 week, 3 days in advance of the event date, and lastly on the event date.

Reflections and limitations/challenges

The venue is bar & restaurant style and we set up the chairs and tables in a casual way. Finger food and beverages were provided, and the audiences seemed to enjoy it. The challenge at the Library BKK was the audio issue. The number of microphones was insufficient. Also, this was our first time to hold the event bilingually (in Thai and English). This caused confusion to some of the audiences. We will revisit this pattern in our next events.

Output and Conclusion

The Pint of Science Shot Thailand took place on 5th November 2024 from 6PM – 8.30PM. There were 5 speakers gave the presentation at the event. The hosts were Thailand Director, Wirichada Pan-ngum, Massaya Sirimatayanant, and Supa-at Asarath from Thailand team.

Prior to the start of the event, the final rehearsal for the speakers and organizing team to quickly run-through the event, to tests the slides, and made sure that all speakers would have control over their slides and made sure that all is set and done. The final rehearsal took place 30 minutes before the starting of the event.

During the event and Q&A sessions after the talks were done, the Kahoot! game was used as a tool to interact with the participants. The audience seemed to enjoy this very much.

There were in total participants 89 at the event. It was the largest number since we have held the Pint of Science in Thailand.

Evaluation report / Feedback from audience

2024 PINT OF SCIENCE THAILAND SHOT
Tue Nov 5th, 2024, 6-8 PM
Library BKK, BTS Victory Monument Exit 4
Join us for a night of science, drinks, and good company. Enjoy free snacks and beverages. Free entry. All are welcome!

SPEAKER AND TOPIC:

- **Adun Samathi:** Theropod Dinosaurs from Thailand (Talk will be in Thai)
- **Phrutsamon Wongnak:** The Rise of Paper Mills: A New Threat to Research Integrity
- **Preeyarach Klaytong & Chalida Rangsiwutisak:** AMASS (AutoMated tool for Antimicrobial resistance Surveillance System) : ชวนวิจัย สู่ใช้จริง (Research to Reality) (Talk will be in Thai)
- **Juthatip Wiwattanapantuwong:** Power to live with disasters: The studies in Thailand and Japan

SPEAKER PROFILE:

- Adun Samathi, Lecturer, Walailak Rajabhat Botanical Research Institute, Mahasarakham University
- Phrutsamon Wongnak, Data Analyst, Clinical Trial Unit, Mahidol-Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit, Faculty of Tropical Medicine, Mahidol University
- Preeyarach Klaytong, Research Assistant and Chalida Rangsiwutisak, Junior Programmer at Microbiology, Mahidol-Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit, Faculty of Tropical Medicine, Mahidol University
- Juthatip Wiwattanapantuwong, Lecturer, Faculty of Psychology, Chulalongkorn University

REGISTER NOW!

(Registration is required.)

MORU Tropical Health Network | W | PINT OF SCIENCE

Pint of Science Shot online promotional poster

Where did you see, hear, or learn about our event? / คุณพบ ได้ยิน หรือรู้เกี่ยวกับงานของเราจากที่ไหน

21 responses

How well did Pint of Science do to increase your interest in science? / งาน Pint of Science

ช่วยเพิ่มความสนใจของคุณด้านวิทยาศาสตร์ได้ดีแค่ไหน?

21 responses

Venue: How do you like this venue? / สถานที่ : คุณชอบสถานที่จัดงาน ในวันนี้มากน้อยเพียงใด?

21 responses

Speakers: in general, how well did they do at serving you science? / วิทยากร: โดยรวมแล้ว

วิทยากรได้ให้ความรู้ด้านวิทยาศาสตร์ได้ดีเพียงใด?

21 responses

Overall enjoyment or 'good time' you had this evening?

โดยรวมแล้วคุณรู้สึกสนุกสนานกับงานในค่ำคืนนี้หรือไม่?

21 responses

What should we definitely do again next time?

Language & Accessibility

- Translation when the speakers present in Thai
- Providing English translations of questions and answers from time to time
- Mix of English & Thai speakers—but visuals should be in both languages

Event Format & Organization

- The format of the talks
- Freestyle talks with food and drinks
- The dual speakers were really helpful

Content & Topics

- Various interesting topics from different fields
- Topics are not too specific—easy to digest
- I like the diversity of talks

Logistics & Hospitality

- Coupons for non-alcoholic beverages
- The kind service of staff members

Overall Experience

- Want to have more events like this
- Knowledge-sharing aspect was valuable

What can we do better next time?

Language & Accessibility

- Applying earphones and one interpreter for a translation
- Regularly ensuring Thai conversations are translated into English
- Maybe have Thai/English summaries of the presentations for those that don't speak the language? (Doesn't even have to be printed, it can be an online document accessible through a QR)
- The language should've been done in an international language. Because this session is open admission for all types of people and foreign people to meet and to grab new knowledge around science with a stress-free environment. Why not English?
- I think the idea of hybrid languages is great. But that needs to ensure the slides are totally followable (and entertaining) for someone who doesn't understand the language the presenter is presenting in. Or, there needs to be a live AI subtitle?
- It's a really inclusive event. However, as a foreigner, I felt a bit lost in the presentations in Thai language.

Venue & Space

- The venue this time might be a little bit tight comparing to numbers of people attending. The slide show might be a bit small for people far away.
- Space is too tight to mingle.
- Too limited seats
- Better venue management, i.e. seating

Timing & Scheduling

- Not on a school night or earlier

Engagement & Interaction

- Want to have ice-breaking activity, and activities that allow participants to mingle and talk among each other before the event started

Content & Topics

- Would love to mix in some hard topics easily explained through this platform too (as to make science close to the public)

Logistics & Event Experience

- More coupons
- Ask audience to remain silent and attentive throughout. At times it was difficult to follow a presentation because others were conversing.

Any other suggestions?

Venue & Space

- Larger space

Event Format & Timing

- Shorter and more concise talks, keeping to time

Language & Accessibility

- I really wish all of the speakers on all topics would speak in international languages. Because the topics are interesting, but I cannot understand the important details which speakers would like to share today. Moreover, I cannot do the quiz better besides guessing. So this provides unfairness to all audiences who cannot understand due to the sharing sessions. I hope this feedback will help the organizers find ways to improve.

Engagement & Networking

- Name tag with topics that the person is working on or topics of interest

Food & Drinks

- Greater drink variety. I was tired and wanted a hot coffee. Could I have brought my own?

General Feedback

- I enjoyed the night. Thanks for the effort. I know it is a lot of work.

Reported by Supa-at Asarath and Rita Chanviriyavuth

Pint of Science Laos 2024

Pint of Science Laos returned for the third year running, hosted by LOMWRU at Corebeer, Vientiane, Laos, on the 13th and 14th May 2024. The event was standing room only, as over 130 people attended each night – the biggest Pint of Science Festival yet for Laos. As part of the global event being held across 25 countries and over 500 cities, Pint of Science Laos had six amazing speakers over the two-night event, with talks from LOMWRU (melioidosis), Elephant Conservation Center (elephant reproduction in Laos), New Zealand-ASEAN Renewable Energy Facility (energy efficiency and conservation in Laos), WWF (fish welfare in the Mekong river), Dam Dam Coffee, as well as a NASA Citizen Science Project (Exoplanet Watch). As previous years, junior staff from Molecular, Microbiology, and clinical teams at LOMWRU organised and hosted the successful event, providing them experience in event organisation, management, and public speaking.

The Pint of Science Laos team 2024 comprised of: Tamalee Roberts, Vilaiphone Phomsisavath, Bountoy Sibounheuang, Vilayouth Phimolsarnnousith, Padthana Kiedsathid, Latsaniphone Boutthasavong, Vilason Souvannasen, Aphaphone Adsamouth, Mayulee Thalongsenchanh, Manila Souksavanh, Souksakhone Volavong, Anousone Douangnouvong, Danoy Chommanam, Vayouly Vidhamaly, Ooyanong Phonemeexay, Malavanh Vongsouvath and Matt Robinson.

7) Malaria World Exhibition in Oxford

MORU intern Shuma Banik led the Malaria World Exhibition at the John Radcliffe Academic Centre in conjunction with World Malaria Day. The exhibition was held from 22nd to 29th April 2024. More details can be found at below links.

- Malariaworld Exhibition: <https://zenodo.org/records/12724240>
- Graphic booklet : <https://zenodo.org/records/12731883>
- Mara and Dara video: <https://zenodo.org/records/12751835>
- The exhibition is now online on the MESH website: <https://mesh.tghn.org/malaria-home-page/>

F) Empirical Bioethics Research

1) Study update *“Melioidosis Vaccines (MeVa): Attitudes to vaccines, melioidosis and clinical trials in key stakeholders in Ubon Ratchathani, Thailand”*

This study aims to gather the perspectives of a key population relevant to clinical trials of melioidosis vaccines; diabetes patients in Ubon Ratchathani; on melioidosis, vaccination, and taking part in clinical trials for melioidosis vaccine; all in prior to beginning the Phase II of the clinical trial for melioidosis vaccine. This study is an explanatory qualitative study, utilizing qualitative research methodology tools, which include in-depth interviews (IDIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs). Participant observations may be observed during the focus group discussion. Field notes may be taken when necessary and possible.

Data collection for MeVa study ended in May 2024, with 71 participants taking part in study.

In May 2024, the study team organised a patient and public involvement (PPI) session with the same group of people who attended previous PPI session in February 2023. The session aimed to inform about study updates, including revisions to data collection methods based on suggestions from first PPI session, total number of participants recruited, and early emerging themes from collected data.

Napat and Supa-at attended the 10th World Melioidosis Congress held at Darwin Convention Centre, Darwin, Northern Territory, Australia, 21st – 23rd October 2024. The congress organised by Menzies School of Health Research and early findings of MeVa study were co-presented by both on third day of congress under “Melioidosis and its Impact on Public Health” theme.

2) *MIST-Ethics*

MIST-Ethics has continued its activities during 2024, which is including data collection, data analysis and dissemination. Data collection included a serie of in-depth interviews with enrolled participants in MIST 1 and MIST 2 during their stay in and after discharged from hospital. All interview data were transcribed and coded through the reflexive process of thematic analysis to examine themes and patterns of meaning within data. This data analysis process was done by the three main MISTE project team members including Supanat Ruangajorn, Natinee Kulpijit and Dr. Bhensri Naemiratch. The peer reviewed article was accepted to be published in BMC Medical Ethics in December 2024 (<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-024-01160-7>).

3) *Strengthening gender equality and social inclusion across the AMR intervention and implementation research continuum*

The project was completed in November 2023. One peer-reviewed article from the project was published in Monash Bioethics Review (refer to publication section).

Dr Bhensri Naemiratch has been asked from IDRC and ICARS to continue providing technical support on integrating gender equity and social inclusion (GESI) lens to their two funded projects in Thailand, including shrimp phage and swine vaccine. The initiative is aimed at reducing the emerging risk that AMR in animals poses to global health and food security. Two specific objectives are i) support research that will identify and develop prophylactic and therapeutic innovative veterinary solutions, including vaccines, to improve health, while reducing the use of antimicrobials in ruminants and aquaculture operations; and 2) build effective, gender-balanced partnerships to better contribute to the discovery and development of innovative veterinary solutions to reduce the use of antimicrobials in ruminants and aquaculture operations in LMICs.

4) *Just Transitions for AMR*

MORU hosted a “Just Transitions” meeting in Bangkok in February 2024. All outputs and details are listed on the British Academy website. <https://www.thebritishacademy.ac.uk/projects/just-transitions-to-contain-antibiotic-resistance-while-minimising-potential-burdens-and-harms/>

5) *Ethics and data sharing*

Naomi Waithira, supervised by Phaik Yeong has completed data collection on the ethical and practical challenges of reusing secondary data. 13-15 March 2024, we organized the Reuse Qualitative Analysis Meeting with MORU Data Management team and OUCRU team, Ho Chi Minh, Vietnam

G) Presentations and webinars by team members (as speaker, key note speaker, panelist or organizer)

- 7th December 2023, Bhensri Naemiratch (MORU) and Ingrid Lynch (HSRC). Webinar: “A Practical Pathway for Change: Learning how to integrate a gender and equity lens in AMR research projects”.
- 14th December 2023, two MIST1 volunteers were invited to attend JITMM to share their experience in the session “Update on Human Infection Models in Thailand”.
- 19-21 February 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah and BE team hosted the Migration Ethics Workshop, Bangkok, Thailand.
- 19 March 2024 – 15th June 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah acted as the ethics expert at the The Archaeology Ethics in Southeast Asia Workshop series organized by SEAMEO Regional Centre for Archaeology and Fine Arts (SEAMEO SPAFA).
- 8-10 May 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah presented “Embedding voices of communities in research priority setting” at the Priorities 2024 organized by Health Intervention and Technology Assessment Program (HITAP).
- 13 May 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah attended the “Priority setting roundtable” with Joe Millum and Katherine Littler (WHO) online.

- 29-30 May 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah attended “Controlled Human Infection Studies in the LMIC Ethics and Regulatory Ecosystem: Role, Conduct, and Utility of Models” Virtual Workshop.
- 7 June 2024, Bhensri Naemiratch and Tassawan Poomchaichote presented “Responsive Dialogues: the framework for ‘AMR Dialogues’ in Thailand”, at the 9th Engagement Thailand Annual Conference, Chiang Mai, Thailand.
- 13 June 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah and Kanpong Boonthaworn presented “Unintended consequences of AMR awareness initiatives: experience from AMR awareness campaigns for World AMR Awareness Week”, the 4th National Forum on Antimicrobial resistance, Bangkok, Thailand.
- 19-23 June 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah acted as the experted reviewer at the “NIHR Global Research Professor Selection Committee”, United Kingdom.
- 27-30 August 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah was a visiting scholar at the University of Darussalam, Brunei.
- In August 2024, Napat Khirikoekkong presented “Early findings of Melioidosis Vaccine in Thailand: A qualitative study of vaccine hesitancy and acceptance and perception of participation in clinical trials among key stakeholders in Ubon Ratchathani Province, Thailand (MeVa study)” at the Global Health Bioethics Network summer school, held at Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.
- 11-12 September 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah, Anne Osterrieder, Bhensri Naemirach, Napat Khirikoekkong, Supa-at Asarath, Supanat Ruangakajorn and Rita Chanviriyavuth organized 2nd CAB – NET Facilitator meeting, Bangkok, Thailand.
- 12 September 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah spoke at the GloPID-R/CERCLE Roundtable Meeting on Data Sharing (organized by Pandemic Sciences Institute, University of Oxford) online.
- Napat Khirikoekkong and Supa-at Asarath gave an oral presentation at the 10th World Melioidosis Congress on “Early findings of Melioidosis Vaccine in Thailand: A qualitative study of vaccine hesitancy and acceptance and perception of participation in clinical trials among key stakeholders in Ubon Ratchathani Province, Thailand (MeVa study)” under “Melioidosis and its Impact on Public Health” theme”. The congress was organised by Menzies School of Health Research in Darwin, Northern Territory, Australia, 21st – 23rd October 2024.
- Westwood, E., Humboldt-Scotland, S., Barake, E., Heriazon, A., Naemiratch, B., Lynch, I. “Integrating gender and equity in One Health and sector specific AMR intervention and implementation research projects in low- and middle-income countries” (poster presentation). 8th World One Health Congress - Cape Town, 20-23 September 2024.
- 4th – 6th November 2024, Bhensri Naemiratch was invited to provide training on “Enhancing Actionable Strategies for Integrating Gender and equity in AMR intervention and implementation research. Participants included representative from ICARS grant recipients from six countries including Zimbabwe, Ghana, Kenya, Malaysia, Thailand, Lao PDR, and Pakistan.
- 7-8 November 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah provided a keynote address at the “AMR Research Symposium”, Singapore.
- 18-20 November 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah attended the “lobal Forum Bioethics Research” annual meeting, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia as member of the Steering and Planning Committees.
- 28 November 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah presented "Antimicrobial Resistance Awareness Week 2024" at Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand.
- 3-4 December 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah attended NiVoT Stakeholder meeting organized by Path Organization, Bangkok, Thailand as an ethics expert.

H) Data sharing

In 2024, there were a total of 19 data request applications. PY Cheah is the coordinator of the DAC with support of Rita Chanviriyavuth.

I) Training and capacity-building

1) Training delivered by B&E

Introduction to Public Engagement

We delivered our online training session “Introduction to Public and Community Engagement and Involvement” in English, on 16th October 2024. It was facilitated by Anne Osterrieder, Napat Khirikoekkong, Kanpong Boonthaworn and Supa-At Asarath. In total, 11 MORU staff and PhD students attended the session.

One bespoke in-person training session was run on 16th December 2024 with 8 participants from the Southeast Asia Bioethics Network (SEABioN), with the aim to develop an engagement strategy and plan, which is part of the network mission.

Science Communication Workshop

In a collaborative effort to enhance staff communication and engagement skills, a comprehensive two-day Science Communication Workshop was held at SMRU, Mae Ramat, Tak province, on April 4th and 5th, 2024. The workshop was delivered by Kanpong Boonthaworn, Supanat Ruangkajorn, and Napat Khirikoekkong, together with Sasipim Arttayakul from the Training and Development department. The workshop objective aims to improve storytelling skills through the use of art, cartoons, and drawing including engagement using materials available in the local areas to ease of tools creation. The workshop benefited 17 staff members operating in the Thai Myanmar border area.

A condensed version of the workshop was later conducted by Kanpong Boonthaworn on September 8, 2024, specifically for 10 staff members working on the school mental health project.

Date	Site	Number of attendee	Main language (s) used	Brief description of participants
12 th Oct 2024	Online	11	English	MORU Tropical Health Network students and staff
16 th Dec 2024	In-person	8	English	Public/community engagement training and development of SEABioN engagement strategy
4 th 5 th April 2024	In-person	17		SMRU staff members operating in the Thai Myanmar border area
8 th Sept 2024	In-person	10		Staff members working on the school mental health project
	Total	46		

2) Engagement and bioethics training attended by B&E

- Supa-At Asarath: Basic Life Supports (English session), Fire drill training delivered at MORU.
- Tassawan Poomchaichote: Understanding and Utilizing ChatGPT training (Feb, 24), Understanding and Dealing with Workplace Bullying and Harassment training (May, 2024), Fire safety and fire extinguisher training (Aug, 2024).
- The B&E team attended an online training session on ‘Child Protection and Safeguarding’, presented by Long Pham Ngoc (OUCRU), 4th June 2024.
- Bhensri Naemiratch, Nipaphan Kanthawang, Supa-At Asarath, Mental Health First Aid Training, 8-17 May 2024.
- Rita Chanviriyavuth: Information Governance, NetSuite Inventory Training, Mental Health Training at SMRU in June 2024.

3) MORU CAB-NET

In 2024, we launched a network to bring together facilitators and coordinators of our community advisory boards (CABs) across the MORU Tropical Health Network. To date, the network met twice online on 13th June and 9th Dec 2024, and in person at MORU Bangkok from 11-12th Sept 2024. It currently has 23 members. Each meeting featured presentations and updates from each CAB, and discussions on shared experiences and challenges, such as how to recruit and engage group members, evaluation strategies, or training and capacity-building needs.

4) B&E Engagement Journal club

In 2024, the B&E Journal Club discussed five papers. The aims of the Journal Club are to provide training in identifying and critically reading academic journal papers, to study examples of how engagement projects can be written up for publication, and to support capacity-building by discussing current topics in engagement and involvement. It meets every two months, and presenters rotate.

9 th Jan 2024	Tassawan Poomchaichote Mitchell, J., Cooke, P., Ahorlu, C., Arjyal, A., Baral, S., Carter, L., ... King, R. (2021). Community engagement: The key to tackling Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) across a One Health context? <i>Global Public Health</i> , 17(11), 2647–2664. h
30 th April 2024	Napat Khirikoekkong Vargas C, Whelan J, Brimblecombe J, Allender S. Co-creation, co-design and co-production for public health: a perspective on definitions and distinctions. <i>Public Health Res Pract</i> . 2022;32(2):e3222211.
25 th June 2024 (joint MAEMOD Journal Club)	Bhensri Naemiratch Collins, C. S., & Stockton, C. M. (2018). The Central Role of Theory in Qualitative Research. <i>International Journal of Qualitative Methods</i> , 17(1).
27 th Sept 2024	Anne Osterrieder Garcia-Iglesias, J., Beange, I., Davidson, D. et al. Ethical considerations in public engagement: developing tools for assessing the boundaries of research and involvement. <i>Res Involv Engagem</i> 10, 83 (2024).
11 th Dec 2024	Natinee Kulpijit Goldberg EM, Rosen RK, Dizon DS, Langdon KJ, Davoodi NM, Wray TB, Nugent NR, Dunsiger SI, Ranney ML. Using Social Media for Clinical Research: Recommendations and Examples From the Brown-Lifespan Center for Digital Health. <i>J Med Internet Res</i> . 2022 Jun 13;24(6):e35804.

5) MORU Community and Public Engagement (CPE) Theory of Change and impact case studies

In 2024, the team worked together with consultants from the 'Institute for Methods Innovation' (IMI) to co-create a Theory of Change (ToC) for MORU's community and public engagement programme. The ToC visualises how our key activities and enabling factors will contribute to achieving our short- and long-term outcomes and impact for the communities and partners that we engage with, and for the MORU research programme. The ToC will underpin our CPE activities during the next core grant period 2025-2032 and formed the basis for the CPE proposal in the MORU core grant application.

We produced two engagement impact case studies for the core grant application: 1) "The Transformative Impact of Community Advisory Boards (CABs) on Research Outcomes and Health Services in the MORU Network" and 2) "Enhancing Consent Processes for Hill Tribe Communities in Northern Thailand through Engagement and Co-creation".

J) MORU PE Bursary Scheme

In 2024, we awarded one MORU PE bursary to the MOUCRU team in Myanmar. All bursary projects from Round 2 have now finished.

Project	Name	Amount	Project end date
Community engagement to understand and improve HIV and sexual health care among women engaging in high risk sexual behavior, in suburban Yangon, Myanmar.	Dr Ni Ni Tun Dr Yinmon Htun (MOCRU) Dr Nyan Lynn Tun (MAM/MOCRU) Dr Thidar Tun (MAM) Ms Zin Zin Htet (MAM) Ms Htet Htet Aung (SMRU)	GBP 6,300	31 st Dec 2024

J) B&E communication and stakeholder engagement activities

1) Annual MORU PE Day

On 8th February 2024 we held our first "MORU Tropical Network Public Engagement Day". The aim of this new annual event is to showcase public and community engagement projects run by our staff and students, inspire those new to engagement to consider their own projects, and facilitate sharing of experiences and learning. The event was held at the Pullman Hotel in Bangkok and attracted over 50 attendees, in-person and online.

Presenters:

- Welcome - Phaik Yeong Cheah
- MORU Tropical Network – Nick Day

- Introductions and ice breaker – Supa-at Asarath
- Wellcome Strategy - Beenish Shaik and Lara Clements, Wellcome Trust
- Tak Province Community Ethics Advisory Board - Napat Khirikoekkong
- ‘AMR Dialogues’ – Tassawan Poomchaichote
- 3-Minute-Thesis - Pawadee Boonyakanjanapon, Meiwen Zhang, Witchayoot Huangsuranun
- Co-creation of a community health calendar in Buntharik - Massaya Sirimatayanant & Monnaphat Jongdeepaisal
- New collaborations and directions – Phaik Yeong Cheah
- School engagement and mental health - Worarat Kuenpetch and Richard Maude
- Triple artemisinin therapy for malaria – policy maker engagement - Chanaki Amaratunga
- Chiangrai Hilltribe Advisory Board - Carlo Perrone, Nattida Toonin
- Health Research Ethics Interest Group – Supanat Ruangajorn
- Co-creating participant information sheets with the community – Nipaphan Kanthawang, Kanpong Boonthaworn
- MORU PE Bursary Scheme and PE capacity building – Anne Osterrieder (virtual)
- Public engagement in rural Cambodia: new directions – Tom Peto

2) MORU Science Seminar

20th May 2024: “Returning to the Principles of Good Randomized Clinical Trials”, Rachel Hallett (Protas) and Evelyne Kestelyn (OUCRU)

16th Sept 2024: “Antimicrobial Resistance, Justice, and Science Communication”, Prof. Marina Joubert (CREST, Stellenbosch University), Kanpong Boonthaworn, Tassawan Poomchaichote, and Prof. Sonia Lewycka (OUCRU)

3) Print materials

- The MORU PE brochure “Working with communities, advisory groups, policy makers and partners” was updated in Dec 2024, and printed for distribution at the Wellcome exhibition. URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/14776703>
- Flyer with T-CAB member profiles, produced for the Wellcome exhibition 2024.
- Various posters for the Wellcome exhibition (map of MORU CABs, CABs, MeVA PPI, etc).

4) Videos

Topic	Additional information	URL
Engaging with community advisory boards at Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filmed in Dec 2024 • Short version • Length: 4:36 minutes 	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aJa0Nswp480

Engagement with the communities at the Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filmed in Dec 2024 • Long version • Length: 10:30 minutes 	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dITXuJ2dWdA
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5) Social media and websites

The B&E project team has established a dedicated Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/saranasuk>) to enhance communication and engagement with key stakeholders in Thailand. This platform, currently boasting over 515 followers and a reach of 66,800 in 2024, serves as a central hub for disseminating information about B&E project activities, research findings, and related knowledge. With a growing audience and expanding reach, this Facebook page aims to strengthen stakeholder engagement, promote the impact of B&E projects within the Thai context, and foster a community interested in the project's work.

K) Meetings and workshops attended

- 22-24 January 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah attended “AI Health Research Ethics Oversight Exceptionalism?” organized by Faculty of Law, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
- 24 January 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah attended the Southeast Asia Bioethics Network Steering Committee meeting, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
- 28 May 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah attended “INSIGHT Webinar: Ethics in Science and Health Communication and Engagement” online
- 25-28 June 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah attended an AMR-related meeting organized by Institut Pasteur, Paris, France
- 9-10 July 2024, Phaik Yeong Cheah attended the Oxford Global Health & Bioethics International Conference organized by Ethox, Oxford, the United Kingdom
- Napat Khirikoekong, Anne Osterrieder and Bipin Adhikari attended the Wellcome “Convening on Community Engagement” Meeting in London, 4th– 8th March 2024. They also were MORU representatives on the Wellcome/ITAD Technical Working Group to co-create a Wellcome Community Engagement Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (MEL) framework. Phaik Yeong Cheah was a member of the steering committee.
- Napat Khirikoekong and Supa-at Asarath attended a seminar on “Implementation of Immigration Law: Impact of Immigration Law Enforcement and Solutions for Immigration Issues” on 20 May 2024 at the parliament building. The seminar was organised by Thailand Migration Reform Consortium (TMR) Topics discussed include challenges in implementation of immigration law toward refugees and migrants, experience of being mistreated, and how the immigration law make them more vulnerable.
- Bhensri Naemiratch and Tassawan Poomchaichote attended the 9th Engagement Thailand Annual Conference ‘Driving Society Engagement Innovation toward Sustainability’, 6th– 8th June 2024, Chiangmai, Thailand.

Annual Report of The Community and Public Engagement Department (CPE), Shoklo Malaria Research Unit and The Borderland Health Foundation (SMRU-BHF)

The Community and Public Engagement Department (CPE Department) in SMRU-BHF is a bridge to connect SMRU-BHF and communities, by supporting quality healthcare services along with humanitarian assistance to the migrant populations along the Thai-Myanmar border and supporting researchers on community engagement in research. Our key responsibilities are to promote and deliver health knowledge, and understanding of research with communities by providing translation, establishing networking, and providing capacity building. Through multiple means of engagement to increase, stimulate, and prevent misconceptions on a health basis.

Overall objectives of the CPE Department

- Promote health knowledge, education, and awareness toward migrant populations, emphasizing Malaria, Maternal and Child Health (MCH), Tuberculosis (TB), and communicable diseases
- Provide translation support across departments
 - Promote understanding of research with communities
 - Inform and share research findings and outcomes
- Establish partnership networks, and maintain good relationships, and collaborations with local organizations existing along the Thai-Myanmar border: Thai Public Health, CBOs, and NGOs
- Capacity building for team members, Community Health Workers (CHWs), and stakeholders: religious leaders, teachers, village head to maximize their abilities to deliver meaningful engagement to target populations

CPE mission:

- Strive to create a good working environment and maintaining good collaboration with partnership network
- Delivering meaningful knowledge and empowering marginalized populations to have comprehensive understanding on health knowledge and healthcare services.
- Strengthen the knowledge and capacity of community health workers and volunteers about health-related issues for ownership and sustainability.

1. Deliverable engagement activities

1.1 Raising Malaria Awareness through Malaria Awareness Campaign Implementation

To increase knowledge about malaria, we conducted 8 malaria awareness campaigns with 580 participants participating along the Thai-Myanmar border. This malaria campaign was approached from a monthly meeting discussion point with the Mae Ramat District Public Health Office (MRM-DPHO). According to the updated malaria report, six malaria Plasmodium Falciparum (PF) cases were found in Ban Ku Ther Tha, Sam Muen Sub-District. In considering the ongoing efforts to control malaria in the Sam Muen Sub-District, especially in providing health education on malaria, the CPE team was highly willing to participate with them to control the PF outbreak.

This activity was led by DPHO, with public health personnels covering the area, while our team supported by delivering the message in local languages (Burmese and Karen). The main message was: “For fever lasting 24 hours or within two days, patients must see Malaria Post Workers for a malaria diagnostic test.”

1.1.2. Raising awareness campaign on Mass screening and treatment (MSaT)

Following a report on the malaria outbreak by the Malaria Department of SMRU, on June 29, 2024, the CPE team conducted malaria campaign activities and supported the operational procedures for MSaT in the two villages of Plaw Hta and Ka Pler Kwee, Area 3, Zone 6, in Southern Karen State, Myanmar. The team members conducted an MSaT campaign activity of eliminating and reducing the PF outbreak which participated 245 representatives.

District/ township	Total Session	Children (Under 18-year-old)		Adult (Above 18-year-old)		The number of participants
		Male	Female	Male	Female	
Mae Ramat	8	84	84	199	213	580
Kawkareik	2	45	47	87	66	245
Grand Total	10	129	131	286	279	825

Table 1: Number of participants and sessions attending Raising awareness campaign on Mass screening and treatment (MSaT)

Challenges:

- The team encountered challenges due to differences in the accents of the Karen language (Myanmar lowland Karen and Thai-Karen) between the villagers and the facilitator, which led to some participants not fully understanding the information provided.
- The time for engaging and preparing material was short, our team encountered challenges in using written information materials when engaging with the MRM-DPHO, the population has low literacy, and other suitable and effective methods to convey health information must be further explored and produced specifically for them.

1.2. Adolescent pregnancy movie “The Journey of Young Leaves”

Our team, together with MCH team collaborated with the SMRU-BHF media team to transform a dialogue drama on adolescent pregnancy into a short film. This film named, “The Journey of Young Leave”, was used as a tool to engage with SMRU-BHF clinic staff at Maw Ker Thai, Wang Pha, Maw Per Koh, and Shwe Kout Kou clinics, in order to increase clinic staff understanding on the adolescent pregnancy issue, allowing them to transfer the meaningful information to the pregnant women or patients and to promote PE activity and engage with clinic staff who working in SMRU-BHF clinic base. As part of our efforts to engage staff in discussions on sensitive topics like adolescent pregnancy, which often remains unspoken, we used various tools and materials. A short film is an effective way to communicate these messages thoughtfully while also providing entertainment.

District/ Township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification	Total numbers of Participant
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		Health Service Provider (s)	Community Health Worker(s)	NGOs/CBOs	SMRU-BHF	Community Leader(s)	Community Member(s)	Male	Female
Mae Sot	1	-	-	-	34	-	-	7	27
Tha Song Yang	1	-	-	-	34	-	-	12	22
Phop Phra	1	-	-	-	68	-	-	18	50
Myawaddy	1	-	-	-	50	-	-	16	34
Grand Total	4	-	-	-	186	-	-	186	

Table 2: Numbers of Participants during Adolescent pregnancy movie

Our team supported the MCH team in organizing movie screenings for communities in Phop Phra, Mae Sot, and Mae Ramat Districts, reaching 933 participants across 24 migrant clusters. After the screenings, feedbacks were gathered to reflect on the film's visualization, content and screening atmosphere. From feedbacks gathered, participants suggested to include information on Thai legal aspects of safe abortion, the rights of young pregnant individuals to access healthcare.

District/Township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification						Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Provider(s)	Community Health Worker(s)	NGOs /CBOs	SMRU-BHF	Community Leader(s)	Community Member(s)	Male	Female
Mae Sot	3	-	8	-	10	-	88	40	66
Mae Ramat	3	32	5	-	8	-	52	42	55
Phop Phra	16	25	65	-	70	-	456	264	352
Umphang	2	-	36	2	10	3	63	29	85
Grand Total	24	57	114	2	98	3	659	933	

Table 3: Number of participants and sessions attending adolescent pregnancy movie show activity at migrant clusters

1.2.1. Raising awareness on Hand Foot Mouth Disease (HFMD)

An outbreak of Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease (HFMD) was reported at the Phop Phra District, Tak province. As the number of HFMD cases increased, many individuals sought for treatment at nearby health facilities.

In response to HFMD outbreak, our team cooperated with the MCH team and gathered HFMD information from articles and online sources. We worked together to translate and simplifying technical terms, and created handmade posters under the supervision of MCH and clinical doctors.

Our team implemented the awareness campaigns on HFMD targeting migrant populations which focused on communities located far from healthcare facilities and in MCH outreach sites. We used role-playing and two-way communication by allowing active participation and engagement from the migrant communities. Instead of just delivering information, we organized and encouraged open discussions where participants could ask questions, share their experiences, and clarify their concerns. We reached 14 migrant clusters, with 1,137 people participating in Phop Phra and Mae Sot Districts.

District/ Township	Total Session	Children (Under 18-year-old)		Adult (Above 18-year-old)		The number of participants
		Male	Female	Male	Female	
Mae Sot	3	40	40	22	133	235
Phop Phra	11	102	111	233	456	902
Grand Total	14	142	151	255	589	1137

Table 4: Number of participants and sessions attending raising awareness campaign on HFMD

Challenges:

- Due to the arrest of documented migrants in the area, our team was advised by AST to reschedule our campaigns and avoid the period which local authorities conducted the arrest targeting undocumented migrants.
- To align with community availability, our movie screening session had to be adjusted many times, this was to ensure high participation in our engagement and movie screening sessions.
- Movie screening session took place in the community where family come together. Some brought their children along and as the screening proceeded, parents became distracted and had to attend to their children. To ensure high participation from participants who came with their children, our team introduced children's activity in hope to eliminate distractions for parents while watching movie.

1.3. Using short movie for awareness campaign and engagement activity

Border populations such as villagers and migrant workers along Thai-Myanmar border is living with high burden of TB, and they have lack of TB health knowledge. In response to this health burden, Tuberculosis Department of SMRU-BHF conducted outreach mobile screening in hard-to-reach areas along the border. Prior to each TB X-ray mobile screening activity, as a mean to motivate villagers and migrant workers to take part in the TB X-ray screening, raise health knowledge on TB, we carried out the awareness campaigns in the targeted communities.

The campaign aimed to:

1. Increase awareness of TB among migrant workers along the Thai-Myanmar border.
2. Promote early diagnosis and control of the spread of TB.
3. Encourage active participation in early TB screening and diagnosis.

In these campaigns, we used a short movie titled “A Silver Lining Hope”, which was produced by our team, involving TB doctors and media team. This movie was a central tool to convey TB health messages. The messages in the movie includes TB signs and symptoms, prevention method, treatment, the danger of the disease, and encouraging early detection and control of its spread.

During the gathering time, our team welcomed the participants and shared snack and juice to the participants so that if they were hungry, they could have it. In hoping to build trust and close relationship with participants involved in the movie, we first introduced ourselves and the organization involved in this campaign.

We then facilitated for open conversation for pre-test assessment to allow the participants to share their understanding and views on TB disease. Following the discussion, we screened the TB movie where we hope that the participants would capture the important messages containing in the movie. Participants appeared smiley and very happy during the screening session. After the movie screening, we conducted post-test assessment questions to evaluate how much they could answer them, and if they gained more understanding of TB before and after watching the movie.

The questions were used for assessment:

1. Have you ever heard about TB?
2. How is tuberculosis transmitted?
3. What are the signs and symptoms of TB?
4. Can TB be cured? How?
5. Do you know any organizations that provide TB treatment? What are they, and where?
6. If diagnosed with TB, would you be willing to seek treatment at a treatment center?
7. What can you do to help your community be free of TB?

From the assessment, participants could answer the questions after watching the movie and would remember each name of actors. We provided token of appreciation to those who participated in the discussion session. During the discussion, we gave plenty of time for participants to ask questions about the movie, and TB information. Before concluding the activity, we prepared a catchy motto in Karen or Burmese which we used throughout our campaign. The motto in English, it means:

**“To eliminate tuberculosis,
Early identification, Early diagnose, Early Treatment, Early recovery”**

Migrants and villagers were happy throughout our whole campaign session and through this motto, they could remember very well about TB health information and would repeat this phrase. We thanked all participants for their present and great participation and reminded to spread the TB information to their neighbors and family members who didn't come.

Despite lots of children coming to the campaigns, we could control children moving in and out not to distract their parents because we had storytelling, drawing and coloring activity for child corner. While children were busy with their own activity, parents and young adults could focus on the TB movie show.

In 2024, from January to November, we conducted 24 sessions of TB awareness campaigns with 3,170 participants in Mae Sot, Mae Ramat, Phop Phra Districts, Tak Province, Thailand, some sessions were conducted in Hpa Pun District, Karen State, Myanmar.

During TB health awareness campaign, our team received strong support from migrant leaders, Thai community leaders, village heads, and community health workers. They assisted with arranging and cleaning venues to ensure a well-organized, clean, and safe space for the movie screening. Additionally, they helped inform migrant population about the campaign. Village chiefs and migrant leaders, along with community health workers, appreciated the valuable activity organized for the migrant community and expressed their willingness to collaborate with us in the future.

District/Township	Type of Activity	Total Session	Children (Under 18-year-old)		Adult (Above 18-year-old)		The number of participants
			Male	Female	Male	Female	
Phop Phra	TB awareness campaign	10	158	186	538	691	1573
Mae Sot	TB awareness campaign	2	39	52	52	284	427
Mae Ramat	TB awareness campaign	3	33	23	94	170	320
Hpa Pun	TB awareness campaign	9	54	86	322	388	850
Grand Total		24	284	347	1006	1533	3170

Table 5: Numbers of participants attending awareness campaign in Thailand and Myanmar

Challenges:

- Audiences attended the event spoken in different Karen accents, thus, some sessions required longer time to ensure understanding between facilitators and audiences.
- Due to unstable political situations and ongoing attacks in the area, this raised safety concerns for our engagement sessions planned for Karen State, in Myanmar.
- Lack of interest and participation among adult working migrant male observed toward TB awareness campaign. Likely contributed by their tight working schedules and they typically returned home in the evening, between 5-6 pm, where they usually need time to cook and rest after a long day of work.

1.4. Awareness Campaign on Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI)

In collaboration with relevant authorities, CPE team provided health information about vaccines to communities along the Thai-Myanmar border, aiming to ensure effective immunization coverage among

children. In 2024, we conducted 48 awareness activities, with total of 2692 participants to enhance understanding of vaccine efficacy and coverage, using simplified messages and localized communication.

Aims of the Sero-surveillance Awareness Campaign:

- To determine the proportion of children in the surveyed population who have received vaccines included in the Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI).
- To estimate the proportion of children in the survey population who have protective antibodies against preventable diseases.

To prevent misconceptions, our team simplified technical terms, shortened messages, and delivered them in local languages through various campaign methods such as community discussion, awareness campaigns. Additionally, we developed Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials, including printed vinyl banners and handmade posters in Burmese and Karen.

Aims of EPI campaign

- Provide information to migrant populations emphasizing EPI vaccination consisting of immunization and preventable diseases.
- Establish and maintain health collaborations with migrant communities, Thai authorities, and Thai healthcare organizations.
- Facilitate distribution of EPI vaccinations to targeted populations.

District/Township	Type of Activity	Total Session	Children (Under 18-year-old)		Adult (Above 18-year-old)		The number of participants
			Male	Female	Male	Female	
Myawaddy	Sero-surveillance awareness campaign	36	499	521	353	580	1953
Kawkareik	Sero-surveillance awareness campaign	10	138	155	161	199	653
Mae Ramat	EPI awareness campaign	1	3	3	13	16	35
Kawkareik	EPI awareness campaign	1	21	18	8	4	51
Grand Total		48	661	697	535	799	2692

Table 6: Numbers of sessions and participants attending awareness campaign in Thailand and Myanmar

2. Filling the gaps and strengthening relationships with partners

2.1. Meeting and discussion on Twin Village along the Thai-Myanmar border meeting on Malaria Elimination at Tak and Mae Hong Son Provinces.

Malaria cases along the Thai-Myanmar border in 2024 continued to rise compared to 2023, mainly because the unstable political situation and continued fighting forced villagers in Myanmar to constantly flee across the border, resulting in the rise of Malaria among this population. Our team and Malaria teams participated in Thai-Myanmar border twin village project meetings aimed at malaria elimination along the border. Key participants of these meetings included the District Public Health Office (DPHO), Umphang Hospital, Vector-Borne Disease Control Center (VBDC), Sub-District Health Promoting Hospitals, World Vision Thailand (WVTF) and Karen Department of Health Welfare (KDHW). Meetings focused on sharing malaria data, planning elimination strategies, reviewing malaria posts, and ensuring sufficient malaria medicines for villagers.

In 2024, our team attended eight malaria meetings in Tak and Mae Hong Son Provinces. These meetings were participated by representatives speaking Thai, Karen, and English languages. To ensure clear communication, our team supported interpretation and facilitation during the meeting. Additionally, we supported coordination with the Thai Public Health Office.

District/ township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification					Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Providers	Communit y Health Worker(s)	Community Leader(s)	NGOs/CBO s	SMRU- BHF	Male	Female
Umphang	5	30	14	-	-	20	28	36
Mae Sot	1	32	-	-	-	3	20	15
Mae Sariang	1	7	-	-	1	2	9	1
Sob Moei	1	16	-	-	19	16	38	13
Grand Total	8	85	14	-	20	41	160	

Table 7: Numbers of meeting and participants attending meeting and discussion on twin village along Thai-Myanmar border

2.2. Stakeholder meeting on Maternal and Child Health (MCH)

Our team maintained close coordination with local authorities and community leaders, which helps us gain access to targeted areas and address community needs. We continued to engage with key contact persons, including elders, village chiefs, employers, and CHWs. Building trust with these stakeholders enabled us to identify new migrant clusters and provide support.

In effort to ensure delivery of antenatal care services to migrant women facing challenges with traveling risks and increase their accessibility to care, our team gave effort in continuous engagement and consultation with communities in Phop Phra, Mae Sot and Mae Ramat Districts. This effort aimed to deliver services in a form of outreach with MCH team, to offer antenatal care for pregnant women, and vaccination for new born.

District/ Township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification					Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Providers	Community Health Worker(s)	Community Leader(s)	NGOs/ CBOs	SMRU-BHF	Male	Female
Mae Ramat	2	23	1	-	-	4	22	6
Mae Sot	2	-	-	-	-	33	9	24
Grand Total	4	23	1	-	-	37	61	

Table 8: Number of meetings and discussion attending meetings and discussions on MCH

2.3. Stakeholder meeting and strengthening relationship with key stakeholders

In promotion of TB knowledge and increasing participation in TB screening activities, our team engaged with local authorities and local stakeholders to obtain permission for a movie screening activity. Movie screening aimed to raise TB awareness in migrant communities and villages before conducting mobile TB X-ray screenings. Our team engaged with public health officials, community leaders, other organizations, and community health workers and gathered data on local health concerns and TB cases. Regular engagement with these stakeholders contributed to strengthening collaboration and promotion of TB health initiatives. We also organized an exhibition showcasing our work with the local community and community leaders at Mae Ramat to mark and celebrate the long-term partnership of healthcare promotion. In total, 16 stakeholders' meetings were organized with 172 key stakeholders such as Public Health Officials, village leaders, in the Hpa Pun District, in Myanmar and Mae Ramat, Mae Sot, and Phop Phra Districts, in Thailand.

Regular meetings between our team and TB outreach team aimed to discuss migrant health issues, sharing population census updates, and planning for TB awareness campaigns and screenings. Reaching communities in mountainous areas remained a challenge due to bad road and limited human resources in our team. We were not able to conduct engagement and screening in these areas, and we will continue to discuss with Mae Ramat hospital and local stakeholders for further planning. We aim to deliver engagement and screening in this area in 2025.

District/Township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification					Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Providers	Community Health Worker(s)	Communit y Leader(s)/ members	NGOs/ CBOs	SMRU- BHF	Male	Female
Mae Sot	2	2	4	2	6	7	13	8

Phop Phra	4	6	4	1	-	9	15	5
Mae Ramat	5	8	19	55	-	23	43	62
Hpa Pun	5	3	1	12	-	10	25	1
Grand Total	16	19	28	70	6	49	172	

Table 9: Meeting and discussion with stakeholders, village leaders and local health authorities to establish new locations of TB case finding

2.4. Engagement with stakeholders on Addressing Vaccine-Related Misunderstanding and Community Engagement

2.4.1. Addressing Vaccine- Related Misunderstanding

Recognizing the impact of misinformation on vaccine confidence, our team took proactive approach to engage with the community and rebuild trust. A meeting was organized in Huay Pla Kong village, Mae Ramat District, where concerns had arisen following an Adverse Event (AE) in a child after vaccination. This incident led to widespread hesitation toward future vaccinations.

To address these concerns, we collaborated and engaged with local community leaders to facilitate open discussions, clarify misconceptions, and provide accurate information about vaccine safety. Our team explained that the AE was unrelated to the vaccine and was instead linked to the child's pre-existing health condition. By fostering transparent communication and ensuring that community voices were heard, we helped restore confidence in vaccination and strengthened local engagement.

District/Township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification					Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Providers	Community Health Worker(s)	Community Leader(s)	NGOs /CBOs	SMRU-BHF	Male	Female
Phop Phra	4	10	37	3	4	45	47	52
Myawaddy	2	-	33	14	-	13	38	22
Grand Total	6	10	70	17	4	36	159	

Table 10: Consultation meeting with local leaders and key persons

Outcome of the Meeting:

- The discussion successfully addressed community concerns, allowing local leaders to share accurate information about vaccine safety and effectiveness.
- Community members appreciated the transparency and reassurance, leading to renewed confidence in vaccination. As a result, they agreed to participate in the next round of vaccinations organized by Thai Public Health personnel.

District/Township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification					Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Providers	Community Health Worker(s)	Community Leader(s)	NGOs/CBOs	SMRU-BHF	Male	Female
Mae Ramat	1	1	-	1	-	3	5	-
Grand Total	1	1	-	1	-	3	5	

Table 11: Stakeholders meeting for Addressing Vaccine-Related Misunderstanding at Huay Pla Kong village

2.5. Site visit, Engagement, Consultation and Informing with Thai Public Health Organization (TPHO), Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), local authorities, Community leaders, Village Health Volunteers (VHVs) and Community Health Workers (CHWs)

As part of maintain working relationship with partners, our team conducted engagement sessions with DPHO, VBDC, and NGOs, including local authorities, community leaders, VHVs and CHWs. These engagement sessions occurred through site visits. During these engagement and site visits, 900 mosquito nets were distributed to migrant villagers. In 2024, our team conducted 9 engagement and 2 site visit sessions, where 61 representatives attended.

In support of Malaria Elimination Task Force (METF) Department to manage requests for malaria medications and G6PD testing training, our team closely working with METF and served as mediator between MEFT and focal persons in the community. Our collaboration with MEFT and malaria partners resulted in the success in delivering G6PD and malaria refresher training to 46 Thai public health officers, and 34 CHWs on malaria radical cures in Mae Ramat District. This partnership and collaboration strengthened our partnership with TPHO and other NGOs working on malaria elimination in these areas.

District/ township	Total sessi on	Participants number – Occupational Identification						Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Provider(s)	Communit y Health Worker(s)	NGOs/ CBOs	SMRU- BHF	Community Leader(s)	Community Member(s)	Male	Female
Phop Phra	4	7	10	-	14	3	-	20	14
Mae Ramat	7	59	34	-	28	-	-	69	53
Grand Total	11	66	44	-	42	3	-	156	

Table 12: Number of participants and site visit, consultations, Informing and training

2.5.1. Consultation and informing for the G6PD survey

We collaborated with SMRU researchers to support malaria Plasmodium Vivax (PV) cohort study activities focused on radical cure awareness. In November 2024, a G6PD survey to screen for G6PD deficiency in three communities in southern Karen State, Myanmar, was conducted. In total 794 community members from three villages participated in G6PD screening surveys. The survey took place during the daytime and evening when community members returned from work.

Information-sharing sessions occurred while participants were waiting for their results of G6PD. Our team deployed different methods, such as informal small group discussions, individual discussions, and handmade posters to deliver information on G6PD. The topics of PV information sessions were delivered including G6PD and its deficiency and why villagers need to be tested. Each participant received a G6PD card with their G6PD status written on it, which would indicate that they took part in Vivax Elimination with Tafenoquine (VET) study or receiving service at Malaria Post.

District/ township	Total sessi on	Participants number – Occupational Identification						Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Provider(s)	Community Health Worker(s)	NGOs/ CBOs	SMRU- BHF	Community Leader(s)	Communit y Member(s)	Male	Female
Kawkareik	3	-	4	-	12	2	91	39	60
Grand Total	3	0	4	-	12	2	776	794	

Table 13: Number of participants and informing about G6PD survey in community in Southern Karen State

Challenge:

- The malaria program in Karen State, Myanmar, has been established by SMRU since 2014. The program mainly focuses on the technical aspects, emphasizing training on malaria, G6PD, and Rapid Diagnostics Test (RDT), supplies of medicines, G6PD test kits, RDT test kits, and evaluating the performance of malaria posts.
- Due to a lack of consistency in community awareness activities, the understanding and knowledge of malaria within the communities have been neglected. Local authorities, such as village leaders, local malaria field supervisors, and healthcare providers, are not sufficiently involved in awareness campaigns. Villagers/community members in this area have low literacy and are unable to differentiate between malaria, fever, and the common cold. This highlighted the importance of the continuation of the Malaria awareness campaign and involving local authorities such as village leaders and health providers to help communicate the message to the communities.
- The survey activities were carried out during harvesting season, where villagers/community members were occupied with harvesting their crops and many were unable to participate in the survey and activities. This resulted in low participation which did not meet the target of the activity.

2.6. Site visit, Collaboration for Larva survey activity

Our team members collaborated with Mae Ramat Hospital, CHWs and VHVs for dengue disease control and prevention. This activity was conducted once a month in eight sections located in Mae Ramat Sub-District.

District/ Township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification						Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Provider(s)	Community Health Worker(s)	NGOs/ CBOs	SMRU -BHF	Community Leader(s)	Community Member(s)	Male	Female
Mae Ramat	4	-	66		16	-	-	56	26
Grand Total	4	-	66		16	-	-	82	

Table 14: Number of participants and sessions on site visits and collaborations with Mae Ramat Hospital for Larva survey activity

2.6.1. Engagement with Key Informants in seeking information regarding to MCH

In 2024, we visited 13 migrant clusters in Mae Ramat Sub-District and 4 migrant clusters in Phop Phra, one clinic was visited in Tha Song Yang. The site visits involved migrant cluster leaders, pregnant women, community members and CHWs. The sessions focused on 1) access to antenatal care for pregnant women, 2) vaccine for children under the age of 5, and 3) where do they usually seek healthcare services for common illness. Total of 26 engagement and consultation session were held, with 163 participations from these community involved in these sessions.

Key findings this year included:

1. Most pregnant migrant women in Mae Ramat buy health insurance schemes from Mae Ramat (MRM) Hospital, resulted in the reduction of attendance at the Wan Pha(WPA) clinic for ANC.
2. Children under the age of 5 in Mae Ramat (MRM) communities received vaccines more often at MRM Hospital and Anamai than at WPA Clinic.
3. Migrants with common illnesses visited (MRM) Hospital or private clinics.
4. Migrants (both adults and children) in MRM communities were increasingly using M-Fund insurance and hospital schemes.

District/ Township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification						Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Provider(s)	Community Health Worker(s)	NGOs/CBOs	SMRU -BHF	Community Leader(s)	Community Member(s)	Male	Female
Mae Ramat	18	-	1	-	54	1	43	62	37
Phop Phra	6	2	2	-	21	13	15	29	24
Mae Sot	1	-	2	-	4	-	2	3	5
Tha Song Yang	1	-	-	-	6	-	-	4	2
Grand Total	26	2	5	-	85	14	60	163	

Table 15: Number of participants and engagements on MCH

2.7. Site visit, Engagement and consultation with stakeholders for raising TB awareness and chest X-ray screening

To maintain connectivity with the community and identification of new migratory clusters, our team consulted with key community members, such as village heads, migrant leaders, health volunteers, and other influential figures. We conducted site and community visits, engaging in 23 sessions with 511 participants in 2024.

Prior the conducting TB awareness campaign and TB chest X-ray screening, our team visited these communities, and held consultation meetings with village heads, migrant leaders, and community health volunteer. These meetings allowed us to meaningfully engaged and listened to their advice. It is a platform for them to share information with us, gaining better understanding of the local context, and for us to inform them on the purpose and expected outcomes of our activities.

Throughout engagement with community leaders and stakeholders, we learnt that they were not aware of active or suspected TB cases. They reported common seasonal health issues such as coughing, colds, and flu due to weather changes. A major healthcare challenge was travelling difficulty, especially during emergencies such as pregnancy, injuries, or critical health conditions.

District/ Township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification						Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Provider(s)	Community Health Worker(s)	NGOs/CBOs	SMRU- BHF	Community Leader(s)	Community Member(s)	Male	Female
Mae Sot	6	-	5	-	11	1	11	11	17
Phop Phra	8	-	-	-	31	41	-	58	14
Hpa Pun	11	30	37	41	34	142	142	228	198
Grand Total	25	30	42	41	76	184	153	526	

Table 16: Engagement with community health workers, key persons and community leaders on TB disease raising awareness

2.8. TB chest X-ray and screening in migrant communities

The SMRU-BHF TB treatment center or sanatorium, known as TB Village, located in Mae Ramat, provides free treatment to underserved populations. The TB department plays a crucial role in treating TB patients, conducting case finding, and providing early diagnosis through mobile TB chest X-ray screenings in migrant communities along the Thai-Burma border. This intervention aims to raise TB awareness and reduce the incidence of TB among marginalized and vulnerable populations free of charge. The TB outreach team and team our worked hand in hand ensuring to deliver X-ray screening to the hard-to-reach population and treatment one diagnoses were confirmed.

In 2024, 20 TB chest X-ray screening sessions were conducted, with 2,450 participants in the Thailand. Before X-ray screenings, our team collaborated with village heads and migrant leaders to arrange the venue and set up screening site. Our team involved in coordinating and consulting with key persons from these communities and maintained close communication with community leaders to ensure local need related to TB health was addressed.

After the screenings, together with TB team, we contacted patients for patients follow and conducted further consultation and counselling. Our team also shared the results of the TB screenings, diagnoses, and treatment outcomes with relevant parties, including the Thai Public Health Office and Sub-District Health Promoting Hospitals. Our team conducted movie screening at other communities where TB screening had not taken place, and in 2025 TB outreach team plans to expand chest X-ray screenings in these communities.

District/Township	Total sessions	Children (Under 18 years)		Adult (Above 18-year-old)		Total number of participants
		Male	Female	Male	Female	
Phop Phra	15	49	75	704	769	1597
Mae Sot	5	55	92	315	391	853
Grand Total	20	104	167	1019	1160	2450

Table 17: Number of participants and sessions on TB chest X-ray and screening

Challenges:

- Migrant workers prioritize working and earning to make ends meet and to support their families, taking part in TB activities were seen as unimportant to them, as such, some screening resulted in low participation.
- We encountered challenges collaborating with employers of migrant workers. They appeared to be unaware of TB and our activities, in some cases, they did not allow their employees to take part in the X-ray screening.

3. Strengthen capacity of PE team members and Community Health Workers (CHWs)

3.1. Capacity Building for CPE team members and relevant departments

Building team capacity is crucial for improving performance and empowering members to communicate key messages effectively. To strengthen the skills and confidence of our team members and colleagues from other departments, we focused on capacity building across various topics. This approach aimed to enhance our team's ability to conduct community activities efficiently and confidently.

We encouraged the members to practice their public speaking and facilitation to deliver effective messages in sharing certain information. This improved how they perform to facilitate and engage with communities while delivering health knowledge.

Our team also kept a close relationship with the Shanti Volunteer Association (SVA) which provided storybooks to our team in which we used to apply storytelling skills in community activities. We received training from SVA before, focusing on storytelling to engage children. By adopting the SVA storytelling method, we could engage and delivered health information smoothly with no disturbance of participants' attention. and it created a positive learning environment. This approach also supported the long-term dissemination of important health information.

District/Township	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification						Total numbers of Participant	
		Health service Providers	Community Health Worker(s)	Community Leader(s)	NGOs, CBOs	SMRU-BHF	Teacher (s)	Male	Female
Phop Phra	1	-	1	3	-	4	-	5	3
Mae Sot	2	-	1	-	3	6	-	6	6

Grand Total	3	-	2	3	3	10		20
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Table 18: Community engagement on establishing TB-HIV and adolescent movie production, and engagement with SVA

3.2. Empowering and Strengthening the Capacity of Community Health Workers (CHWs) and Malaria Post Workers (MPs)

Umphang hospital shared that CHWs and MPs in their responsible area had limited understanding of malaria diagnosis, data recording and reporting system. They were not able to fill out weekly report, G6PD and daily logbooks which impacted malaria surveillance and reporting in the area. As this work relied mainly on the efforts of MPs in the area, their capacity and skills needed to be strengthened. Our team, together with METF and Umphang hospital organised 7 training sessions for 184 CHWs and MPs. Contents of these trainings include malaria diagnosis, data recording and reporting system. Training venues were in villages in Umphang District. Two training delivered in March and one in June. The training also aimed to equip CHWs and MPs workers with necessary knowledge, as well, to empower them in tackling malaria and enhance their knowledge and skills in conducting malaria diagnosis contributing to malaria elimination in their responsible area.

Location	Type of Activity	Total Session	Children (Under 18-year-old)		Adult (Above 18-year-old)		The number of participants
			Male	Female	Male	Female	
Ta Per Pu	Malaria & G6PD, RDT Training	3	-	-	30	54	84
Lay Taw Ku	Malaria & G6PD, RDT Training	3	-	-	30	45	75
Poeng Khloeng	Daily logbook, Weekly report and G6PD logbook Training	1	-	-	9	16	25
Grand Total		7	-	-	69	115	184

Table 19: Empowering and Strengthening the Capacity of Community Health Workers (CHWs) and Malaria Post Workers (MPs)

Challenges:

- Umphang located near Thai-Myanmar border and has unstable mobile signal, as such, communicating with focal persons in the area via telephone remained a challenge
- Data recording form used and produced by METF team was not understandable by CHWs and MPs, this was captured during the training; hence, our team provided another refresher training
- Reporting forms and systems are new and unfamiliar to CHWs and MPs. After the training, to ensure accuracy of reports, Umphang hospital and METF team should closely observed and continue to provide support needed.

1) 3.2.1. Capacity Building for CPE Team Members

Our team focuses on disseminating health information, supporting research, and facilitating community engagement for Thai-Myanmar migrant communities. To ensure continued success, team members

participated in capacity-building activities, including refresher training, workshops, and knowledge-sharing sessions, in collaboration with SMRU, MORU, and external organizations. These initiatives aimed to improve workplace performance and individual competencies, enhancing the effectiveness of public engagement efforts. 34 activities were conducted in 2024, which helped team members build confidence, stayed focused, and achieved their goals in a structured and impactful manners.

Location	Type of activity	Total Session	Adult		Total number of participants
			Male	Female	
SMRU-BHF Office	Training for staff on SRHR	1	9	11	20
SMRU-BHF Office	Training for stay healthy for CPE staffs	2	15	17	32
SMRU-BHF Office	Training of science communication to CPE staffs from MORU	2	24	24	48
SMRU-BHF Office	Malaria Update information Lecture by Prof. Francois	2	41	33	74
SMRU-BHF Office	Refresher Training of (TB, Family planning, storytelling, Teaching Methods, FGD & IDI)	3	33	39	72
SMRU-BHF Office	Thai Public Health Structure Sharing	1	8	9	17
SMRU-BHF Office	Participatory Learning Approach (PLA) for Community, Base on 9 dimensions	1	8	10	18
SMRU-BHF Office	Sero-Survey Sharing Information	1	9	11	20
SMRU-BHF Office	Gender Equality and Social Inclusion Sharing Information	1	8	8	16
SMRU-BHF Office	Focus Group and Individual In-depth Interview training	2	21	42	63
SMRU/BHF Meeting room	Refresher training for Malaria, Daily logbook, and Weekly logbook	2	15	24	39

SMRU-BHF Office	Tafenoquine (TFQ) MDA sharing session	2	23	20	43
SMRU-BHF Office	PECE staff analysis activity	1	11	13	24
SMRU/BHF Meeting room	Entomology Training	2	18	28	46
SMRU-BHF Office	GCP training	2	10	17	27
SMRU-BHF Office	Training Hand, foot, Mouth Disease (HFMD)	1	2	7	9
SMRU-BHF Office	Scabies Disease training	1	4	5	9
SMRU-BHF Office	Basic Microsoft Word and Excel Training	7	42	63	105
Total		34	302	381	682

Table 20: Total trainings/workshop/knowledge sharing for PCE team members

3.2.2. Empowering and Strengthening the Capacity for Community Health Workers (CHWs) and key persons

Our team worked to build trust and enhance the knowledge of CHWs and MPWs We consulted with the Expertise France Initiative (EFI), community leaders, and stakeholders to plan capacity-building topics and secure access to their areas.

Our team conducted an EPI Vaccine Workshop to enhance VHV's understanding of SMRU-BHF vaccines and help them share clear, accurate information about vaccination with the communities.

As a result of these efforts, we conducted one capacity-building session for volunteer health workers, with a total of 36 participants.

Location	Type of activities	Total Session	Adult		Total number of participants
			Male	Female	
SMRU-BHF Office	EPI Vaccine workshop for Community Health Workers (AST)	1	6	30	36
Total		1	6	30	36

Table 21: Empowering and Strengthening the Capacity for Community Health Workers (CHWs) and key persons

4. Collaboration with partner organizations for community engagement events

4.1. Collaboration with Thai Public Health for World Malaria Day

Our team collaborated with Khane Chue's Sub-District Health Promoting Hospitals and World Vision Foundation Thailand (WVFT) on World Malaria Day. We set up booth to present our SMRU-BHF history, our programs, and shared malaria knowledge through Q and A activity. The World Malaria Day attended by 200 community members, 15 health service providers, 50 VHV, and two members of WVFT participated.

4.1.1. Ceremony of MOU sign for prevention and control of malaria and dengue

Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) with Thai Public Health Officials in Mae Ramat District was signed. The MOU is aimed for prevention and control of malaria and dengue in Khane Chue Sub-District, Mae Ramat District. This collaboration included 44 health service providers, and 200 VHV. Our team distributed 200 mosquito nets to community members.

Location	Type of Activity	Total Session	Children (Under 18-year-old)		Adult (Above 18-year-old)		The number of participants
			Male	Female	Male	Female	
Khane Chue Sub-District	Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) sign of prevention and control of malaria and dengue	1	-	-	100	152	252
Khane Chue's Sub-District	World Malaria Day	1	15	20	100	139	274
Grand Total		2	15	20	200	291	526

Table 22: Number of participants attending at World Malaria Day and Ceremony of MOU

4.2. Collaboration with stakeholders for World TB Day and exhibition in community

Our team supported TB team the exhibition and activity on World TB Day at Mae Tao Clinic, in Mae Sot. We brought a spinning game and using game to help audiences learn about TB and how to prevent and treat it. Participants spun the wheel to get the number of a question to answer. We displayed the movie screen at waiting points in hopes that participants would gain knowledge about the signs and symptoms, prevention, and treatment of TB. TB information leaflets were disseminated to audiences during this event. Many watched the movie and participated in Q&As activity in the spinning game. This collaboration marked significant work and engagement our team in showcasing the SMRU-BHF-related work especially on TB and collaboration with local partner fostering health promotion among the border population.

District/Township	Type of Activity	Total Session	Children (Under 18-year-old)		Adult (Above 18-year-old)		The number of participants
			Male	Female	Male	Female	

Mae Sot	Collaboration activity for exhibition on World TB Day	1	19	31	87	176	313
Grand Total		1	19	31	87	176	313

Table 23: Number of participants attending at World TB Day

5. Engagement for Vulnerable; ensuring no one is left behind in health

The project was funded by Expertise France, to be carried out from March 1, 2023, to February 28, 2025, aiming to improve healthcare services for vulnerable populations and respond to emergencies and natural disasters in Hlaing Bwe, Kawkareik, and Myawaddy, townships in Karen State, Myanmar. Key partners include BHF foundation, METF department, and CPE team. The project focused on strengthening the capacity and resilience of local healthcare systems through training health workers and village leaders, enhancing healthcare accessibility, and empowering communities on health.

The project emphasizes the following objectives:

1. Strengthening the capacity of rural health workers and village leaders to respond to emergencies and promote gender equality.
2. Improving access to and utilization of local emergency healthcare services.
3. Increasing resources for vulnerable groups within local emergency healthcare services.

The project team worked closely with CPE members, partner clinics, METF department, and self-help groups to conduct community consultations with stakeholders, including village headmen, local administrative leaders, teachers, health committees, and workers. All partners are involved in organizing capacity-building workshops, health education, and events on focused topics in project targeted areas.

5.1. Raising awareness campaign

Our team collaborated with self-help group members, and local clinics operated by KDHW and KEHOC, and community engagement activities were organized to raise awareness on the topics of diarrhea, malaria, family planning, personal hygiene, child immunization, and scabies. These health engagement sessions were targeted for stakeholders and population. During the awareness campaign, our team applied participatory approach to build trust and foster further activities with community members, stakeholders and health workers. The methods we used in the awareness included Introduction of ourselves, sharing background of our organization and creating a space for the participants through Q and A session. The total 26 sessions of awareness campaigns were conducted, and attended by 2,478 participants from villages in Myawaddy and Kawkareik Districts, in Myanmar.

District/Township	Type of Activity	Total Session	Children (Under 18-year-old)		Adult (Above 18-year-old)		The number of participants
			Male	Female	Male	Female	
Kawkareik	EFI: Awareness - Dengue and TB	3	30	53	21	100	204

Kawkareik	EFI: Awareness - Diarrhea	3	54	62	18	94	228
Myawaddy	EFI: Awareness - Dengue and TB	6	80	95	133	218	526
Myawaddy	EFI: Awareness - Personal Hygiene	2	52	49	50	127	278
Myawaddy	EFI: Awareness - Child Vaccination	2	5	14	49	75	143
Myawaddy	EFI: Awareness - Diarrhea	1	15	15	17	33	80
Myawaddy	EFI: Awareness - Family Planning	1	9	12	10	55	86
Myawaddy	EFI: Awareness - Scabies	3	41	56	89	166	352
Myawaddy	EFI: Awareness - Scabies and village clean-up	5	124	147	137	173	581
Grand Total		26	305	377	415	899	2478

Table 24: Number of participants in overall awareness campaigns

5.2. Engagement meeting and community consultation

Our team collaborated with Local clinics administered by the Karen Ethnic Health Organization Consortium (KEHOC) to host community consultations with local leaders, including health workers, teachers, religious leaders, and other relevant individuals. The consultation was the vital component of strengthening our EFI 5% project's operational activities. The advice and suggestions provided by the stakeholders helped our team to evaluate what we should carry on and what we should carry on in the operational efforts. Besides, these consultations led to the organization of a Training of Trainers (TOT) for Community Health Workers/Malaria Post Workers (CHWs/MPWs), raising health awareness of seasonal diseases identifying by the community and some village leaders and new site expansions.

Location	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification					Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Providers	Community Health Worker(s)	Community Leader(s)	NGOs/CBOs	SMRU-BHF	Male	Female

Hlaing Bwe	3	36	20	34	-	9	73	36
Kawkareik	11	11	25	96	-	43	95	80
Myawaddy	24	49	58	146	0	73	175	151
Chiang Mai	1	0	0	0	2	7	5	4
Grand Total	39	96	114	315	2	146	619	

Table 25: Community Consultation with local leaders, health workers and other relevant persons

5.3. Site visit for project progress reviews and mapping health facilities and characteristics, locations, and means of transport

A needs assessment was conducted to gather insights into health facilities, healthcare services, and the training needs of health workers, village leaders, and the community. This assessment focused on identifying challenges in accessing healthcare services and understanding health knowledge from discussions with community members, community leaders and health workers. Our team conducted individual and small group interviews to assess satisfaction and perspectives on the EFI 5% project and the awareness campaigns, events, workshops, and training-initiated activities. We recruited self-help group members and administrative leaders who had received training and participated in the activities. Snowball sampling was used to recruit key informants for individual interviews, allowing us to gather insights from community representatives on their health concerns and other capacity building needs.

Location	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification						Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Provider(s)	Community Health Worker(s)	NGOs/CBOs	SMRU -BHF	Community Leader(s)	Community Member(s)	Male	Female
Kawkareik	3	-	4	0	13	9	12	19	19
Hlaing Bwe	6	-	39	0	18	147	15	131	88
Myawaddy	6	-	9	5	18	21	23	38	38
Grand Total	15	-	52	5	49	177	50	333	

Table 26: Mapping health facilities, individual and small group discussion

5.4. Capacity Building for CPE members and Self-Help group members

In collaboration with the Karen Environment and Social Action Network (KESAN), the project team organized a Training of Trainers (TOT) for staff from the CPE department of SMRU-BHF, also representatives from self-help groups also attended. The training aimed to equip participants with knowledge of community-based responses to sustainable development in health and livelihoods, and to enabling them to apply this knowledge within their communities.

The project team also conducted capacity-building training for senior CHWs/MPWs and community leaders, focusing on identifying local challenges related to primary healthcare, disease outbreaks, and natural disasters. As part of this training, the team introduced a practical exercise called the "Waste Management Cycle," which not only helped identify local issues but also provided solutions and strategies for project sustainability. Total 13 capacity building sessions were organized as shown in the table below.

Location	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification						Total numbers of Participant	
		Health Service Provider(s)	Community Health Worker(s)	NGOs/CBOs	SMRU-BHF	Community Leader(s)	Community Member(s)	Male	Female
Mae Ramat	3	-	9	6	44	9	-	33	35
Myawaddy	2	-	13	-	8	40	8	35	34
Hlaing Bwe	3	-	87	-	-	-	-	27	60
Kawkareik	5	-	14	-	20	14	49	26	71
Grand Total	13	-	123	6	72	63	57	321	

Table 27: Participants numbers for capacity building training

5.4.1. Workshop with self-help group

Our team conducted the workshops for the key stakeholders and community members for 25 times in Hlaing Bwe, Kawkareik, Myawaddy Districts and Tak province. These workshops aimed to establish and strengthen the network among self-help group members to identify existing emergency and health-related issues. Participants were also encouraged to share their experiences of emergencies (ie., flood, drought, Covid-19 Pandemic, airstrike) that each group had faced and resolved.

Location	Total session	Participants number – Occupational Identification						Total numbers of Participant	
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		Health Service Provider(s)	Community Health Worker(s)	NGOs/CBOs	SMRU-BHF	Community Leader(s)	Community Member(s)	Male	Female
Hlaing Bwe	11	-	43	-	42	175	80	242	98
Kawkareik	6	-	35	-	31	67	1	57	77
Myawaddy	5	-	73	-	24	37	15	62	87
Tak	3	-	-	-	24	-	-	15	9
Grand Total	25	-	151	-	121	279	96	647	

Table 28: Workshops conducted for the community members, community leaders and community health workers

5.5. Organizing village clean-up activity for World Environmental Day Event

“World Environmental Day” was successfully held in nine villages in project areas such as Hlaing Bwe, Kawkareik, and Myawaddy Townships. The event was divided into two sessions: indoor and outdoor sessions. The indoor session included an exhibition of photos of implemented activities and information pictures about environmental hygiene. The project team and self-help group members performed a roleplay highlighting the complications of an unsanitary community, and transmission of infectious diseases. Following the first session, the event attendees and people crossed by were invited to join a village clean-up activity. These activities include trash collection such as canned fish, plastic bags, bottles, and other trash in each village. For this special occasion, our team and the community planted a tree in each village for honoring to World Environment Day.

For second time of village clean-up activity in project year 2, our team prepared a session of health awareness about scabies disease with the aim of enhancing community health knowledge about scabies disease, to understand and adhere the preventive methods, and to reduce from the spreading of scabies disease in communities. Through health awareness session and big village clean-up activities, community members will be able to comprehend the relationship between the environment and health, highlighting the significance of hygiene and sanitation in preventive sickness, pay attention to the importance of environmental hygiene, and finally foster community involvement and collaboration in a health setting.

Location	Type of Activity	Total Session	Children (Under 18-year-old)		Adult (Above 18-year-old)		The number of participants
			Male	Female	Male	Female	
Kawkareik	EFI: Event - Community Engagement with community on	3	80	91	66	96	333

	World environment day and village clean-up activity						
Myawaddy	EFI: Event - Community Engagement with community on World environment day and village clean-up activity	6	99	135	164	243	641
Grand Total		9	179	226	230	339	974

Table 29: Participants numbers in the events

Main successes

- Health coordination meeting with local stakeholders to implement planned activities
- Successfully organized community engagement with stakeholders and target population by promoting health knowledge of Diarrhea, Malaria, family planning, personal hygiene, and Child immunization
- Held coordination meetings with self-help groups for planning health-related activities
- Organized First Aids and management workshop for community members, community leaders and community health workers
- Conducted progress review via individual and small group interviews to identify and understand how well the project's operation is sharing information-related health, awareness campaigns, events, workshops, and training initiated
- Supported emergency cases including pregnant women (referral) and other emergency cases (support food and first aid need for Internal Displaced Persons)
- Productively organized an event, "World Environmental Day" followed by a village clean-up
- Held capacity-building training for CPE team and Self-help group leaders

Main challenges

- Political unrest and insecurity remain in the project areas, which caused delayed the plans
- Transportation and consumables costs increased due to inflation
- Transportation difficulty due to checkpoints of armed groups and village-pass which is a barrier to travel.
- Muddy and bumpy roads during the reporting period delayed the planned schedule.
- limited internet and mobile access in some areas resulted in communication challenge for team.
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6. Materials Development and Contribution to Communities

6.1. Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) Materials/Tools Development

The development of IEC materials is crucial for our team to effectively communicate health education and messages to migrant populations along the Thai-Myanmar border. These materials simplified complex health information, making it accessible and understandable to population with low literacy, and ensuring better engagement and health impact.

Our team developed the handmade or hand drawing posters on the topics including scabies, HFMD and Sero-surveillance and 12 types of vaccine for raising the awareness campaigns in various communities along the border. We produced the posters align with local context and local language use of Karen and Burmese. These posters were made with rice bags which are portable, light and durable to bring to remote areas.

Handmade posters	Total
Scabies	9 sheets
HFMD	6 sheets
Sero-surveillance	2 sheets
12 vaccine types	5 sheets

6.1.1. Addressing Health Issues Through Role Play

We used role-playing as an interactive approach to engage community members in discussions on key health issues such as waste management and diseases like Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease. By acting out real-life situations related to waste management and Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease (HFMD), we simplified complex topics and made them more relatable. This method encouraged active participation, allowing community members to take part or provide input, making learning more engaging and memorable. Additionally, post-session discussions helped reinforce key messages, promote dialogue, and foster a shared sense of responsibility for improving community health.

6.1.2. Creating Visual Tools for Health Education

To address communicable diseases like scabies and Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease, as well as topics like G6PD surveys and Sexual Reproductive Health and Rights (SRHR), our team created visually engaging cartoon illustrations. These illustrations were designed to be culturally appropriate, easy to understand, and visually engaging, ensuring better comprehension and active participation among community members.

In 2024, we conducted 47 sessions focused on developing IEC materials/tools, with the number of participants shown in detailed in the table below.

Location	Types of activity		Adult	Total number of participants
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		T o t a l Session	Male	Female	
Mae Sot, Mae Ramat, Phop Phra	TB, HIV awareness movie production	28	161	142	303
SMRU-BHF Office	Role play practice on world environmental day	1	11	11	22
SMRU-BHF Office	Rehearsal for waste management project workshop	1	6	8	14
SMRU-BHF Office	HFMD material development	2	6	11	17
SMRU-BHF Office	HFMD practice	3	11	11	22
SMRU-BHF Office	Scabies Disease Material Development	7	31	21	52
SMRU-BHF Office	G6PD Survey materials development	3	15	15	30
SMRU-BHF Office	Material development of Training for stay healthy by PE staff and need assessment workshop	2	11	12	23
Total		47	252	231	482

Table 30: Number of participants attending IEC materials/ tools development activity

8. Nine Dimensions course

From March 2022 to October 2023, we applied for a one-year project through the bursary scheme aiming to enhance our capacity for effective community engagement. This funding enabled us to enroll in a course of “The Ethnographer’s Way” taught by Professor Decha Tangseefa respectively, which helped us improve our ability for social science research proposal writing skill. Twelve members of CPE team enrolled in this course where we have learnt how to write proposal and expand our understanding and knowledge of social science on the guiding book of “The Ethnographer’s Way”. Through this course, we gained the skill to write the research proposal and currently, we are conducting two research studies focusing on TB sanatorium and immunization barriers. It is expected that this course will finish at the end of the 2025.